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(1915–1999)**

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ТРУДЫ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО ЭРМИТАЖА
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**МАТЕРИАЛЫ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ
КОНФЕРЕНЦИИ,
ПОСВЯЩЕННОЙ 100-ЛЕТИЮ
СО ДНЯ РОЖДЕНИЯ
ИГОРЯ МИХАЙЛОВИЧА ДЬЯКОНОВА
(1915–1999)**

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Настоящий сборник включает материалы Международной конференции, посвященной 100-летию со дня рождения Игоря Михайловича Дьяконова (1915–1999), которая состоялась в Государственном Эрмитаже и Институте восточных рукописей РАН 13–15 января 2015 года. Состав сборника отражает широту научных интересов И. М. Дьяконова. Статьи посвящены различным областям ассириологии, переднеазиатской археологии и семитологии. В них затрагиваются проблемы политической и социально-экономической истории Месопотамии и сопредельных стран, месопотамской религии и литературы, лингвистики и истории письменности.

Хронологические и географические рамки сборника чрезвычайно широки. Читатель найдет здесь обсуждение теории храмовой экономики Шумера конца 4-го – 3-го тыс. до н. э. и вопросов идеологии Ассирии и Вавилонии второй половины 1-го тыс. до н. э.; культурных контактов Египта и южного Леванта в эпоху ранней бронзы, возникновения и развития царства Урарту, существования скифского государства на древнем Ближнем Востоке. Сборник содержит также статьи, посвященные интерпретации различных терминов и топонимов, встречающихся в месопотамских документах и литературных произведениях; проблемам грамматики хурритского языка и происхождения западносемитского алфавита; аккадско-чадским лексическим параллелям; древнейшим и пуническим надписям. Он ориентирован на широкий круг специалистов, занимающихся изучением истории и филологии Древнего Востока, сравнительно-исторического языкознания.

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THE SCHOLAR AND POLITICS: NABÛ-ZUQUP-KĒNU,
HIS COLOPHONS AND THE IDEOLOGY OF SARGON II

It is a great pleasure to dedicate an article about one outstanding scholar to another. In all epochs scholars were involved, often against their will, into ideological and political propaganda. Igor Mikhailovich Diakonoff lived in times when the relationship of a scholar with power had an especially sensitive character. In this complex situation, he never betrayed human dignity and scholar's obligations to an objective research. I am glad to contribute this study about one of the most prominent Mesopotamian scholars to the centenary volume of Igor Mikhailovich.

It is well known that Sargon II's ascension to the throne brought great changes to Assyria. This king is mostly notable for the innovations dared by none of his forerunners or successors. Among the great changes of Sargon's time is the rise of scribal elite and, consequently, the vast number of compositions that its representatives left to us¹.

The wealth of written evidence from the reign of Sargon is extraordinary. This is true for all kinds of texts and all genres of these kinds. Sargon's scribes resurrected the habit of writing on clay prisms and cylinders, which had been abandoned since the first half of the 10th century². Incredible numbers of these media bearing his royal inscriptions were produced in the reign of Sargon. Moreover, clay prisms and cylinders were not only buried in the foundations of the various buildings of Dūr-Šarrukīn but apparently also sent from the new capital to the other cities of the Empire³. In this period scribes start to create not only royal inscriptions and hymns as previously in the early Neo-Assyrian period, but also royal rituals and epics, like the Assyrian *Enūma eliš*⁴. Sargon's scholars composed, copied or translated from Sumerian a variety of literary and divinatory compositions, including treatises on astrology, extispicy, ornithoscopy and so forth. Sargon obviously aimed at founding the library at his new capital, Dūr-Šarrukīn, as testifies the cover inscription of the set of luxurious ivory writing boards discovered at Kalḫu⁵. He invited Babylonian scholars to the Assyrian court⁶.

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, “the Scribe” (Active 716–684)

The legacy of “the scribe” Nabû-zuqup-kēnu is probably the richest of those left to us by any Mesopotamian scholar. The investigation of the political agenda of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's scholarship was launched by the pioneering article of Eckart Frahm⁷, who explored the connection between outrageous circumstances of Sargon II's death and Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's study of the XIIth tablet of the Epic of Gilgamesh⁸. Soon after, Ann Guinan connected

Fig. 1. Family Tree of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s involvement with the series *If a City is Set on a Height* with Sargon’s Babylonian campaign⁹.

I will argue, however, that Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s investment into royal ideology started much earlier. Nabû-zuqup-kēnu was a scholar at royal service probably from the very beginning of Sargon’s reign. As testify his numerous colophons, he belonged to the lineage of royal scribes and was a descendant of the chief of the scribes, Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the *ummānu* of Tukultī-Ninurta II and Assurnasirpal II (Fig. 1)¹⁰. The first dated tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu is the copy of the 33rd or 36th tablet of *Enūma Anu Enlil* series (716)¹¹, though the tablet in the colophon of which he refers to himself as an apprentice should be of earlier date¹². On almost all his other tablets, the modest title *tuṣṣarru* (^{lu}DUB.SAR)¹³ appears in his colophons after the name of his father, Marduk-šumu-iqīša. This title probably relates to the latter, also because in a number of instances¹⁴ it is followed by the phonetic complement *-ri/-ri*, which might indicate the genitive. However, once in the two-line colophon, which does not contain his patronymic, Nabû-zuqup-kēnu is called ^{lu}DUB.SAR¹⁵. In the colophon of his grandson, Issār-šumu-ēreš, they both have the title ^{lu}A.[BA], “the scri[be]”¹⁶. Once ^{lu}M[AŠ[?].MAŠ[?]], the exorcist, appears together with the usual ^{lu}DUB.SAR after the patronymic, again leaving unclear, if it refers to Nabû-zuqup-kēnu or to his father¹⁷. Finally, a single tablet of

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu bears his title still as ŠAMÁN, the apprentice¹⁸. This unfortunately very badly damaged tablet is the first known commentary¹⁹, *mukallimtu*, *Šumma Šîn ina tāmartišu* 2.

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's descendants were also prominent court scholars. His son Nabû-zēru-lēšir and grandson Issār-šumu-ēreš²⁰ were the chief scribes of Esarhaddon and Assurbanipal, and his other son Adad-šumu-ušur was the chief exorcist of Esarhaddon (Fig. 1). None of them, however, left a textual legacy even nearly comparable to that of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu.

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu was, using Ulla Koch's expression, an "illustrious and industrious" scholar, probably the most industrious in Assyria. Great number of scholarly texts belong to him. So far, I was able to identify 103 of his colophons on a variety of scholarly cuneiform tablets²¹. Among them are the aforementioned XIIth tablet of the Epic of Gilgamesh, and the tablets of the astrological omen series *Enūma Anu Enlil* and *Šumma Šîn ina tāmartišu*, commentaries to the former, tablets from the series of esoteric lore I.NAM.GIŠ.ĪUR.AN.KI.A, the terrestrial omen series *Šumma ālu ina melē šakin*, lung omens *Šumma hašū*, and so forth²². Vast majority of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's tablets deal with divination of different kinds. Astrological-astronomical texts prevail considerably. Terrestrial omens *Šumma ālu* quantitatively are on the second place in his collection. There are relatively few of his extispicy texts. Doubtlessly, Nabû-zuqup-kēnu was a diviner with an expertise in such a wide range of divinatory texts that neither the traditional term for this scribal profession, – *barū*, nor the later term *tuṣṣar* *Enūma Anu Enlil* fully encompasses his erudition.

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's Input in Sargon's Royal Ideology

Many of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's colophons have two distinguished features that point out to the scholar's involvement with politics and ideology of the Empire. The first peculiarity of his colophons are dates, which Alan Millard called "double datings"²³, though those relating to the period after Sargon's invasion of Babylonia are actually "triple datings".

Double and Triple Dates (Appendix 2)

Double dates are the eponym date and the regnal year date, which occur together in a number of inscriptions. That was an attempt at the introduction of the southern Mesopotamian tradition of dating by regnal year concurrent to the *limmu* dating system. Double dating was aimed at the centralization of power. Those who started using double dating belonged to Assyria's highest scribal elite. The first double dates appear in the 6th year of Sargon, 716, and belong to Nabû-zuqup-kēnu himself.

The very first known dated colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu have double dating by the *limmu* of Ṭāb-šil-Ešarra, governor of Assur, and by the sixth regnal year of Sargon, that is 716²⁴. In that same year the other descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the scribe Inūrta-uballissu marked with a double date the colophon of a quite unusual literary composition, the collection of short fables and proverbs, designated by Wilfred G. Lambert as Popular Sayings. This text, found at Assur, was written in the Neo-Assyrian dialect²⁵.

In the colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, the *limmu* date always precedes the regnal year. In general, the order is: the *limmu* year, the regnal year as the king of Assyria. Starting with 709 the regnal year of Sargon, the king of Babylon is added on the colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu.

There is another very remarkable text with a double date. It is the royal ritual ND 1120 found at Kalḫu but deriving from Assur, which was composed in 714 despite the fact that its colophon describes it as the copy of an old original²⁶. The author of the ritual is *Zaia*²⁷, a hereditary scribe of the city of Assur, *tupšar ali*, whose colophon contains the author's extraordinarily long fifteen-tire genealogy²⁸. All ancestors of *Zaia* were the scribes of the city of Assur, except for the family forefather, who was the scribe of the tablet house, *tupšar bēt tuppāti*²⁹.

Date formulas of the ritual composed by *Zaia* bridge between the traditional dating by an eponym and innovative double datings of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu. The double date appears in the colophon, where the *limmu* date precedes the regnal year as it does in the colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu³⁰. The order is reversed in the incipit, but there the first line contains not the exact regnal year of Sargon, king of Assyria, but a general expression *ina taryi*, "in the time of" Sargon, which rather rarely appears in the date formulas of Assyrian documents and colophons starting with Tiglath-pileser III³¹. The eponym date of Issār-dūrī occurs only in the second line.

In order to perform this ritual, the royal scribe, *tupšar šarri*, Nabû-šallimšunu, the author of Sargon's Letter to Aššur specially arrives from Kalḫu. His Letter to Aššur contains the famous account of Sargon's eighth campaign, the campaign against Urartu³². In the ritual, *Zaia* himself and Nabû-šallimšunu, his colleague from Kalḫu, are presenting royal offerings to Aššur and Šamaš. Given that the ritual took place on the 21st of Kislimu (IX) or, more probably, Tebētu (X), 714 and that Nabû-šallimšunu came personally from Kalḫu to participate in it, this ritual was apparently connected with Sargon's Urartian campaign, which was waged or at least started in Du'ūzu (IV) 714³³. By chiasitic dating with the general reference to the "time of Sargon" in the incipit and then the repetition of the regnal date but already in its exact form, *Zaia* wanted to glorify the victorious king, whose triumph the ritual celebrated.

There are only two economic documents with double dating by *limmu* and by the regnal year from the reign of Sargon, but both are remarkable. They are closely connected to the royal court. The first one is a royal land grant to provide offerings for Aššur³⁴. It dates to the 9th of Simānu of the ninth year of Sargon, king of Assyria and to the eponymate of Aššūr-bāni (713). The second is a land purchase deed but the buyer is Nabû-kabti-aḥḥēšu, who bears the title "palace scribe of Sargon, king of Assyria", *tupšar ekalli ša Šarru-kēn šar mat Aššur*³⁵. He acquires an enormous landed estate located near the road to Kalḫu from four people for the huge sum of six minas of silver. Moreover, the tablet was found at Khorsabad. Nicholas Postgate³⁶ assumed that the purchase was in the area of Dūr-Šarrukīn, by then in its final stages of construction. Though Postgate based his assumption on the reading, which is not anymore valid, and we cannot locate the plot, the date of the purchase closely precedes the inauguration of the city in 707 and the deed was stored in Dūr-Šarrukīn, which might be an indication that it was indeed related to the land purchase in its area. The first four witnesses are the scribe of the governor of Kalḫu, the city³⁷ overseer, the mayor of Kalḫu, and the scribe of the queen. The rest of the witnesses on this deed are the servants of the palace and of the magnates. The purchase took place in Kalḫu; it is dated to the eponymate of Mannu-kī-Aššūr-lē'i and to the twelfth year of Sargon that is 709, a year after the invasion to Babylonia.

In this very year the triple dates start to appear in the colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu: the date by *limmu*, by the regnal year of Sargon, king of Assyria and by the regnal year of Sargon, king of Babylon. Nabû-zuqup-kēnu is the only one to ever use the triple dates.

palace scribe from Kalḫu, among the first witnesses of which are the scribes of the governor of Kalḫu and of the queen, is an additional proof of this cooperation. Moreover, the first ones to use double dates were Nabû-zuqup-kēnu from Kalḫu and Inūrta-uballissu from Assur, both descendants of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš. The state's most important scribes endorsed the use of double dating, introduced by Nabû-zuqup-kēnu in 716, even beyond scholarly texts.

After Sargon's death, Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, who was still active as a scholar until 684, continues to use double dating. Triple dating naturally disappears, since Sennacherib officially was not the king of Babylon.

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu put the double dates on the six texts from the reign of Sennacherib, four of them commentaries³⁸. A double dated explanatory text from the time of Sennacherib, prepared by Nabû-zuqup-kēnu for his grandson Issār-šumu-ēreš, the chief scribe of Esarhaddon and Assurbanipal to be, contains excerpts from the esoteric series 1.NAM.GIŠ.ḪUR.AN.KI.A³⁹. This is the last text by Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, and in his colophon he stresses that he strained his sight in order to prepare it.

Apart from the texts of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu himself, there is only one double dated scholarly text from the time of Sennacherib. It is the collection of incantations for a ritual of consecration of the priest of Enlil⁴⁰, copied by a young apprentice, whose name and patronymic are lost, son or descendant of a royal exorcist. This was probably the student of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu or even one of his sons or grandsons. The latter is especially plausible, since the title "exorcist" appears also in the aforementioned last tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, K. 2670 (Appendix 2, no. 16).

Further, double date is found on two copies of Sennacherib's royal inscription⁴¹, written in the eponymy of Nabû-kēnu-ušur / year fourteen of Sennacherib, thus suggesting 703 as his first regnal year. Apparently, these are the copies of the inscription upon the stele erected in honour of the battle of Ḫalulê. This text is the earliest one with the account of Sennacherib's eight campaigns. Its form and style is unique among Sennacherib's inscriptions. No other one of them contains such a detailed description of political events followed by such a short account of construction works. This text also encloses multiple literally allusions to *Enūma eliš*⁴². Thus the author of this inscription was a highly educated scholar, who used his knowledge to create a certain political climate.

Moreover, in the reign of Sennacherib double dating is more widely used in economical documents. Date formulas using eponymy together with the regnal year are attested on three deeds from the time of Sennacherib⁴³. In two cases the regnal year precedes the *limmu* date⁴⁴. There are scribes among the witnesses, but they do not belong to the scribal elite. The exclusion probably is one Nabû-šumu-iddina, who is the first witness on the deed of Aḫi-talli, female administrator (*šakintu*) of Nineveh. The seller in SAA 6 90, Martu', cities' or villages' manager of the queen, is connected with the buyer in SAA 6 177, the royal bodyguard Ulūlāiu. The latter is the witness on the other deed of this villages manager⁴⁵. Worth noting is that Nabû-šumu-iddina is also the tablet keeper of the deed of Mannu-kī-Arbail dated to 676 that is to the reign of Esarhaddon⁴⁶. This tablet is the last one with the double date, and in its date formula the regnal year also precedes the *limmu* date. Nabû-šumu-iddina was apparently the court astrologist, who together with the sons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu and his grandson Issār-šumu-ēreš wrote a letter to Esarhaddon concerning the substitute king ceremony⁴⁷. Thus, again he belonged to the circle of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu.

It is clear that the double dates were introduced into use among Assyrian scribes by Nabû-zuqup-kēnu. Not only was he, together with his relative from Assur, the first to apply them, but the number of his double and triple dated (31)⁴⁸ texts exceeds that with the double dates by all the other individuals together (only 9)⁴⁹ incredibly. Nabû-zuqup-kēnu obviously adopted the tradition of dating by regnal year while copying multiple Babylonian tablets. Moreover, there are astrological reports to Assyrian kings that are dated by their regnal years⁵⁰; all of them are written in Babylonian ductus and those of them from the time of Sargon are dated by his year as the king of Babylon. Finally, one of the copies of *Enūma Anu Enlil* 5, also written in Babylonian ductus by apparently a Babylonian scholar, whose partly preserved name does not belong to anybody of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's family. However, the tablet itself derives from Assyria and is dated by year 4 of Sennacherib⁵¹. As noted before, astronomy and astrology was Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's primary expertise and his dates by regnal year come not just from the Babylonian tradition but also from the astronomical milieu.

The attempt of the scribal elite, and Nabû-zuqup-kēnu in the first place, to introduce a dating system according to the regnal years of the king was not accidental. In the light of the disappearance of the previously most prominent *limmu* officials from the eponym lists, it is clear that the purpose of introducing the double dates was to reduce the importance of the authentic Assyrian *limmu* office and dating by eponyms. The practice of *limmu* dates was a statement of the independence of the magnates⁵². Later, in the time of Esarhaddon, when the institution of the eponymate had lost its importance, double dates, difficult for Assyrian scribes, disappear⁵³. Esarhaddon and Assurbanipal did not even take the eponym office, which is an indication of its decline⁵⁴. Sargon's new scribal elite successfully degraded the symbolic importance of the eponymate by using the authority of the Babylonian tradition of dating by regnal years, focused on the central power of the king.

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu and Sargon's New Capital

In various periods of human history, moving the capital often indicates the king's endeavour to rid himself of dependence upon the old elites of the former capital. Sargon II came to the throne due to the uprising at Assur⁵⁵, as did Tiglath-pileser III due to the riot at Kalḫu⁵⁶. Sargon's striving for independence from Assur and Kalḫu was so strong that he moved his capital to the "middle of nowhere", a place that previously was hardly inhabited⁵⁷. Neither Assurnasirpal II nor Sennacherib, who built new capitals of Assyria prior to and after Sargon, went that far. Both Kalḫu and Nineveh existed before they became capitals. Kalḫu is attested archaeologically in the Middle Assyrian period. It was built by Shalmaneser I or II and served as a provincial capital⁵⁸. Nineveh was an ancient cultic centre at least from the Old Assyrian period⁵⁹. The only other completely artificial Assyrian capital was Kār-Tukultī-Ninurta⁶⁰. Dūr-Šarrukīn was a huge city, comparable with Babylon and Nippur⁶¹. Its enormous walls created almost exact square raised upon a huge artificial mound⁶².

Sargon the Second and the Construction of Dūr-Šarrukīn

Besides double and triple dates, the colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu have another distinctive feature related to royal politics and ideology. The famous astronomer and astrologer called Sargon *arkū*, "following, later, second"⁶³. It should be stressed that unlike us, the cuneiform tradition did not enumerate the namesake kings. Sargon II is the only case, and

this was Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's invention *par excellence*. Nobody but Nabû-zuqup-kēnu calls Sargon "the Second". The only exception is the appearance of *Šarru-kēnu arkû* in 716 in the colophon of Inūrta-uballissu, the "relative" of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu from Assur⁶⁴. Interestingly, *arkû* is applied to intercalary months⁶⁵. It is conceivable that Nabû-zuqup-kēnu derived the term from the astronomical milieu. Later, in the time of Sargon's great-grandson Assurbani-pal, the Elamite king Tammaṛitu was also called *arkû*⁶⁶. Possibly Issār-šumu-ēreš, Assurbani-pal's chief scribe, continued using the term introduced by his grandfather.

Most intriguing is that, despite the scarcity of the evidence for Sargon the Second (*arkû*), this epithet is preserved in a much later source, the so-called Ptolemaic Canon, written in Greek by the Greek astronomer, Claudius Ptolemy, who gives the total of the regnal years of Ἀρχαῖνον, i. e. Sargon⁶⁷. Thus, Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's innovation was so influential that it endured over almost nine hundred years into a different language and culture. This might indicate that the actual application of *arkû* to Sargon was much more widespread than the few colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, which have survived until our days. Most probably, the works of the influential Assyrian astronomer were known to his Babylonian colleagues of the Hellenistic period and were communicated in some form to Ptolemy⁶⁸.

The political implication of this epithet is clearly the allusion to the legendary king and hero, Sargon of Agade⁶⁹. This allusion was a claim for more than just the reflection of the ancient fame. Sargon the Old moved his capital and founded a new dynasty⁷⁰, as did his Assyrian namesake.

In order to justify his king's radical step Nabû-zuqup-kēnu elaborately introduced the allusion to Sargon of Agade, "the Great", whose example Sargon the *arkû* of Assyria followed. According to Irving Finkel and Julian Reade, by following the example of Sargon of Agade and Gilgamesh, "Sargon II, with his new city, was conforming to the pattern of Mesopotamian rulers set on creating a new world-order, and the name he chose for it, Dūr Šarrukīn, confirmed the nature of his aspirations"⁷¹.

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, Cryptography and Dūr-Šarrukīn

We know about Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's interest in numerological manipulations due to his tablets of the explanatory esoteric series I.NAM.GIŠ.HUR.AN.KI.A dealing with celestial matters, which were probably composed by this Assyrian encyclopaedist himself⁷². The double dated colophon of K. 2670 states that Nabû-zuqup-kēnu wrote it for his grandson Issār-šumu-ēreš⁷³. K. 170+ contains the numerological treatment of the names of Sîn. Judging from a partial catch line of K. 2670⁷⁴, of which only the colophon is preserved, this excerpt written in 684 especially for Issār-šumu-ēreš also dealt with the names of Sîn, the deity of a special importance for Sargon's new dynasty⁷⁵.

Sargon's appeal to the perimeter of Dūr-Šarrukīn being a *gematriab* of his name⁷⁶ was another way to propagate the construction of the new capital and invoke the divine blessing on it. The *gematriab* of Sargon's name is most probably also Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's invention, since the latter encrypted his own name and the name of his father Marduk-šumu-ēreš using multiple repetition of the same signs, which should have been diversely pronounced and understood. Thus K. 8173 reads:

9' [...] *ki-i pi-i* ^{giš}*le*₉ - ^{'u}*u*₅ ^{meš} NU UR.A ^{meš} LIBIR.[RA ^{meš} ...]
 10' [...] GABA.RI KÁ.DINGIR.RA ^{ki} ù KUR ^dA-[*šur*...]

11' [...]aš(sic)^dl̄.ZU.ZU-*zu-qup*(DU)-GIN(DU) A aš(sic)^dKU.KU [...]

12' [...i-n]a ta-mar-ti-šú iš-tur [ib-rì-im...]

9' [...]In accordance with wooden boards, unequal in size, ancient cop[ies...]

10' [...]originals from Babylon and Ass[yria...]

11' [...]Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-[šumu-ēreš...]

12' [...]wrote and collated for his reading [...].

Besides the cryptographic writing of the names, this colophon stands out for the use of AŠ instead of DIŠ as personal determinative, which also is attested in Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's colophons of *Šumma Šin ina tamartišu*, *mukallimtu*-commentaries 1 and 4⁷⁷. The use of the rare sign *le*₉ in *le'û* and the writing l̄.ZU.ZU for Nabû might indicate that Nabû-zuqup-kēnu was familiar with the Exorcist's Manual of Esagil-kīn-apli and his work on SA.GIG series⁷⁸.

A similar encrypted writing of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's name appears in the colophon of the *Šumma Šin ina tamartišu*, tablet K. 953 as well:

Rev.

4 [a-na] IGI.LAL-šú ù šī-ta-as-si-šú^{md}l̄.ZU.ZU-*zu-qup*(DU)-GIN(DU)

5 [iš-tur]r o o o ib-rì-im

4 [For] his reading and studying Nabû-zuqup-kēnu

5 [wrot]e and collated.

Series Šumma ālu, Astrolabes and Dūr-Šarrukīn

As was noted above, the series *Šumma ālu* were the main interest of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu beyond astronomy and astrology. Interestingly, all the dated tablets of *Šumma ālu* deriving from his library, were written in 708–707⁷⁹, and there is no identifiable text in his collection written in these years other than *Šumma ālu*. Why did Nabû-zuqup-kēnu dedicate these particular two years to studying the terrestrial omens *If a City is Set on a Height*? Guinan⁸⁰ pointed out that Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's undated Prodigies of the Fall of Akkad⁸¹, i. e. Babylon, relate to Sargon's victory over Merodach-Baladan and gaining control of Babylonia in 710. Continuing her line of thought, I will argue that Tablet 120 of *Šumma ālu*⁸², which deals with processional omens in general and with the *akītu* procession in particular relates to the inauguration of Dūr-Šarrukīn. Indeed, this tablet with a very symbolic number ($12 \times 10 = 6 \times 5 \times 4$ etc.), that might reflect Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's passion for numerology, seems to terminate the series. It has the highest number in the series and is the latest dated tablet of *Šumma ālu*. It was written on Araḥsamnu 16, 707⁸³, the next month after the inauguration of Dūr-Šarrukīn, which took place on Tašrītu 22, 707⁸⁴. A section of Tablet 120 treating the behaviour of a horse⁸⁵ harnessed to the divine chariot obviously relates to the *akītu* procession⁸⁶.

Sargon's inauguration of Dūr-Šarrukīn in Tašrītu was, first and foremost, the introduction of the gods into their new houses. Year 707 was the year of Sargon's return from Babylon with the Babylonian booty and particularly with the booty of Dūr-Iakīn, Merodach-Baladan's home city, subjugated and plundered by Sargon's brother and vizier Šin-aḥu-ušur⁸⁷. All together, it was the triumphal *akītu* of Tašrītu, inauguration of the city celebrated by the introduction of the gods, accompanied by the king and the booty, into the new capital⁸⁸. It also celebrated the final subjugation of Babylonia. Analysing the inauguration of Dūr-Šarrukīn,

Victor Hurowitz concluded that “the celebration is heavily focused on the king” and him receiving the tribute of his subject and vassals⁸⁹. This “triumphal inauguration” took place “In a favourable month, on a propitious day”⁹⁰. Tašrītu 22 is the first day of the fourth, the last phase of the lunar circle, the waning crescent. Araḥsamnu 16, when Tablet 120 of *Šumma ālu* was written is the first day of the waning gibbous, day next to the full moon. Nabû-zuqup-kēnu probably started to write his *Šumma ālu* tablets on Nisannu 15, 708⁹¹, the day of the first full moon of the New Year. All these dates including the inauguration of Dūr-Šarrukīn are related to lunar phases, the numerological exploration of which was undertaken by Nabû-zuqup-kēnu in the second division of I.NAM.GIŠ.ĪUR.AN.KI.A⁹². Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s only hemerological tablet incorporates excerpts from the *Šumma ālu* and *Iqqur ipuṣ* series, which is explicitly stressed in its colophon⁹³.

It is worth noting that the undated *Šumma ālu* tablet, dealing with the behaviour of a sacrificial sheep is of a square form as is the plan of Dūr-Šarrukīn⁹⁴. Square was considered to be a form of an ideal city in antiquity⁹⁵. It is conceivable that the sheep in question were sacrificed on occasion of the inauguration. Even the very title of the series *If a City is Set on a Height* hints to the new Assyrian capital raised upon a huge artificial mound.

It has been already noticed by Hurowitz that the dates in the description of the building of Dūr-Šarrukīn⁹⁶ are taken from Astrolabe B. He also points to the allusions to *Enūma eliš* and the Laws of Hammurabi found in the text and concludes that the scribe who composed it was versed in literary masterpieces and in Babylonian literature in general⁹⁷. Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s proficiency in Babylonian literature is beyond any doubt. He authored the XIIth tablet of the Epic of Gilgamesh that was probably translated by him from Sumerian⁹⁸ and copied numerous Babylonian tablets. Nonetheless, there is no evidence that Nabû-zuqup-kēnu ever composed any royal inscription. The author could be some scribe of his circle, for instance Nabû-šallimšunu⁹⁹, but as a court astrologist Nabû-zuqup-kēnu definitely influenced the process of choosing the dates for building Sargon’s capital. Moreover, he is the author of the circular astrolabe Sm. 162.

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu and the Creation of the Library at Dūr-Šarrukīn

Scholarly texts and tires of niches typical for the library, which were unearthed in two gaterooms of the Nabû temple at Dūr-Šarrukīn, point to the existence of the temple library there¹⁰⁰.

However, the discovery of sixteen luxurious ivory writing boards and the fragments of probably the same number of wooden writing boards in the well at Kalḫu¹⁰¹ drove many scholars to the conclusion that Sargon aimed at establishing the library in his new capital, Dūr-Šarrukīn. This library was intended for the palace as states the title engraved on the cover board of the ivory writing boards (ND 3557). It is particularly important for us that the ivory writing boards found at Kalḫu and intended for Sargon’s new palace contained the text of the series *Enūma Anu Enlil* as the same title says¹⁰². The only person known to copy *Enūma Anu Enlil* in Sargon’s period was Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, who lived and worked in Kalḫu. Thus it was apparently Nabû-zuqup-kēnu who prepared the *Enūma Anu Enlil* copy inscribed on the ivory writing boards and who inspired the creation of the royal library in the new palace of Dūr-Šarrukīn. Most probably he did it in 706, when he returned to copying *Enūma Anu Enlil*¹⁰³, or even in 705. This late date explains also the fact why the

polyphthich was never delivered to Dūr-Šarrukīn. Why the writing boards remained in Kalḫu and were not taken to Nineveh and, moreover, why they were thrown into the well, is an enigma.

Conclusion

Using Guinan's expression, "Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's scholarship appears to reflect the events of the day"¹⁰⁴. Not only did his scholarship reflect the political situation, but it also influenced the latter through shaping the ideology of Sargon's realm. Introduction of the double dates was summoned to facilitate the reduction of the power of magnates and to promote the absolutism that Sargon pursued. Assyrian scribes sometimes related to *taryu*, "the time of" the king¹⁰⁵, but they did not really know how to properly use dating by regnal year. All Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's double dates use only 721 as the ascension year of Sargon and all but one¹⁰⁶ use 704 as the ascension year of Sennacherib. This accords with Sargon's inscriptions that record the same events in Sargon's 15th year as the king of Assyria and his 3rd year as the king of Babylon (707)¹⁰⁷. In the Eponym Chronicle also the eponymy of Mannu-kī-Aššūr-lē'i (709) is the year of Sargon's ascension in Babylon, which took place on occasion of the *akēnu* of Marduk on Nisannu 1¹⁰⁸.

However, the same eponym chronicle records Abu (V) 12 of the eponymy of Nashur-Bēl (705) as the date of Sennacherib's ascension¹⁰⁹. The royal ritual written by Zaia and the deed of Nabû-kabti-aḫḫēšu¹¹⁰ take 722 as the ascension year of Sargon. According to the ritual copied by an apprentice¹¹¹ and the three deeds¹¹², Sennacherib's ascension year was 705. According to the date formula of Sennacherib's inscription, his ascension year was 703¹¹³. It is clear that most of Assyrian scribes perceived as the first regnal year the year when the king became the king *de facto*, and not the year when the official investiture on the occasion of the New Year took place¹¹⁴. The purist Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, however, followed the Babylonian tradition, and counted the first full year of the king as his first regnal year.

Double and triple dates in the colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu aimed at diminishing magnates' prestige and upgrading the royal one. Allusions to the legendary Sargon the Old through the use of the epithet *arkū* in association with Sargon's name hinted that the Assyrian king is as great a hero as was his Akkadian namesake. The appeal to the unequivocal authority of the ancient forerunner justified moving the capital to Dūr-Šarrukīn. Nabû-zuqup-kēnu wrote his *Šumma ālu* tablets exploring the portents that regard the fall of Babylon into Sargon's hands and inauguration of his new capital. Probably, the *gematriah* of Sargon's name as a perimeter of the walls of Dūr-Šarrukīn was also inspired by Sargon's great expert in astrology and numerology. Apparently Nabû-zuqup-kēnu was behind the creation of the royal library in Sargon's new capital. This, however, never happened due to the king's death in battle and abandonment of Dūr-Šarrukīn as a royal residence.

Nabû-zuqup-kēnu was definitely more active and probably, more close to the king in the time of Sargon than in that of Sennacherib. There are eighteen of his dated texts from the reign of Sargon¹¹⁵ and only seven from the reign of Sennacherib¹¹⁶. Naturally, the chronological distribution of the undated tablets remains the subject for further research. In 715–714 and in 710 Nabû-zuqup-kēnu did not write anything, at least not on clay. It seems possible that he accompanied his king in the Urartian and Babylonian campaigns¹¹⁷. Indeed, Nabû-zuqup-kēnu used his enormous erudition to help strengthen and centralize the power of his king and to glorify the king's name.

Appendix 1 Genres of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's Tablets

Listed below are only those of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's tablets, the identification of the genre of which was possible. 25 tablets remain unidentified, among them some colophons' flakes, for which the identification of the genre of the tablet they once belonged to will be never possible. Unless otherwise specified, the identification is based on the colophon data and it remains unclear if the tablet was dated or not.

Literary (705):

Standard Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic, Tablet XII

K. 3475+DT 13+81-2-4, 327; 705.

Divination, general:

DT 318: catalogue of omen incipits (*Oppenheim* 1974¹¹⁸. P. 208, n. 45); 709.

Commentaries, general:

K. 4387: commentaries on *EAE*, *Šumma izbu*, *Šumma ālu* (CCP: <http://ccp.yale.edu/P395521>).

Astronomy:

K. 14971: astrological – on the obverse five lines with the remains of ^{mul}DILBAD preserved; date broken off.

Astrolabe and Mathematical Problem Text Concerning Distances between Stars

Sm. 162: the obverse contains an Astrolabe and the reverse, according to W. Horowitz's suggestion, is a mathematical astronomy problem text¹¹⁹; not dated.

Enūma Anu Enlil (EAE; 716–685; 25 tablets)

K. 2686+K. 2687: colophon – *EAE* 36; *Reiner* 1998¹²⁰. P. 234 – *EAE* 33; 716. 1891, 5-9 Bu, 97; *EAE* 41; 716.

K. 3129: colophon – *EAE* 63(?); *Reiner* 1998. P. 227 – *EAE* 64(?); 716.

K. 2679: *EAE* 6; 713.

K. 2688: *EAE* 17; 709.

K. 5280: *EAE*, *rikis gerri* 6; 709.

K. 5277: *Reiner* 1998. P. 233 – *EAE* 53; CCP: <http://ccp.yale.edu/P395970> – *EAE* 52 or 53; 709.

K. 5281+Rm. 591+K. 1348: colophon – *EAE* 6; *Reiner* 1998. P. 217 – joins *EAE* 6/7; 706.

K. 3044: *EAE* 8; 706.

K. 10084: colophon – *EAE* 34; *Reiner* 1998. P. 248 – *EAE* 33; 706 or 705.

K. 14934+K. 15241+Rm. 497+K. 6457+K. 12416+80-7-19, 90: *Frahm* 1999¹²¹. P. 88–90 – *EAE* Jupiter A; *Guinan* 2002¹²². P. 13 – *EAE* 64(?); 705.

K. 3163: colophon – *EAE*, *rikis gerri*; *Fincke* 2014¹²³. P. 132 – one of the first four tablets of *rikis gerri*; 701.

- K. 398: *Reiner* 1998. P. 17 – *EAE* 56, commentary; 698.
 K. 75+K. 237: CCP: <http://ccp.yale.edu/P237772> – commentary on *EAE* 5(?); 694.
 K. 14169: *Reiner* 1998. P. 266 – *EAE* 57(?); 686.
 K. 3071: *EAE* 34/35(?), *Reiner* 1998. P. 226; Sennacherib.
 Sm. 707a: colophon – *EAE* 26 excerpt; *Reiner* 1998. P. 277 – *EAE* 25; not dated(?).
 K. 5282: *EAE* 36; date broken off.
 Sm. 1239: *Reiner* 1998. P. 279 remarks: “apod.”; *Lieberman* 1987¹²⁴. P. 208, n. 243 – omen text; not dated.
 K. 5283: *EAE* 56; date broken off.
 K. 11867: *EAE*; not dated.
 K. 137: CCP: <http://ccp.yale.edu/P393762> – commentary on *EAE* 58(59)–62(63), *Iqqur ipuš*; not dated.
 K. 9914: CCP: <https://ccp.yale.edu/P398394> – commentary on *EAE* 5(?); not dated.
 K. 15919: *EAE*(?); not dated(?).
 Sm. 1070: *EAE* 12(?); not dated(?).

Šumma Šîn ina tāmartišu (SIT) commentaries (apparently all not dated; 16 tablets)

- Sm. 930: *SIT* 5 (cf. the catch line of the colophon to *Gehlken* 2007¹²⁵. P. 4), *mukallimtu*.
 K. 10379: *SIT* 2, *mukallimtu*, not dated, but probably the earliest of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s tablets, since he is called “apprentice” in its colophon.
 K. 11309: colophon – *SIT* 2; *Rochberg-Halton* 1988. P. 67 – incipit of *EAE* 14; *al-Rawi, George* 1991¹²⁶. P. 58 – incipit of *EAE* 15(?); *Reiner* 1998. P. 254 – *EAE* 14(?); *Gehlken* 2007. P. 4 – incipit of *SIT* 3(?); <https://ccp.yale.edu/P399217> – commentary to *EAE* 14.
 K. 2254: *SIT*, *mukallimtu*.
 K. 1776+K. 6051+K. 10694: colophon – *SIT*, *mukallimtu*; *Reiner* 1998. P. 218 – *EAE* 55, commentary.
 K. 2171+Sm. 780: *SIT* 1, *mukallimtu*.
 K. 7839: *SIT* 1(?), *mukallimtu*; only a flake of the colophon preserved.
 81, 7-27, 81: *SIT*, *mukallimtu*.
 K. 4204+K. 10893: *SIT* 1, *mukallimtu*.
 K. 953: *SIT*.
 K. 14854: *SIT*, *mukallimtu*.
 K. 6686: CCP: <http://ccp.yale.edu/P396730> – *SIT*(?), commentary. This tablet is remarkable for the direction of the inscription on the reverse is perpendicular to that on the obverse.
 K. 2170+K. 03629: *SIT*, *mukallimtu*.
 K. 11614+15788: *SIT*, *mukallimtu* (?; only traces of the colophon preserved on the reverse and Diš 30 of the first line of the obverse).
 K. 2181: *SIT*, *mukallimtu*.
 K. 50: *SIT* 6(?), *mukallimtu*.

Extispicy (712, 711, 704; 7 tablets):

- K. 3068: *Koch-Westenholz* 2000¹²⁷. P. 132, 139–150 – *manzāzu*-commentary 1 (manuscript B); 704.

K. 8014: *Koch* 2005¹²⁸. P. 253–267 – commentary to *multābiltu* 4, CCP: <http://ccp.yale.edu/P397438> – commentary to *multābiltu* 14–15, 8–9, and 7; 711.

K. 7929: *Koch-Westenholz* 2000. P. 116–118 – *manzāzu*.

K. 3041: *Koch* 2005. P. 85–89 – *Multābiltu* Catalogue; not dated(?).

K. 2680: probably *Šumma hašū*; line 17' is exact parallel to *multābiltu* 12–13 (83-1-18, 411):10¹²⁹; 712.

Šumma hašū (all 711)

K. 2678: colophon – *Šumma hašū*; *Koch* 2005. P. 267 – *Šumma hašū* 13.

K. 2683+K. 8083: colophon – *Šumma hašū*; *Koch* 2005. P. 267 – *Šumma hašū* 13.

K. 2692+K. 3164: *Šumma hašū* 3.

Terrestrial Omens:

Šumma ālu (708–707; 16? tablets)

K. 2685+K. 3762+Sm. 1705: colophon – *Šumma ālu*; *Freedman* 1998¹³⁰. P. 159 – *Šumma ālu* 10; 708.

K. 2682+K. 2684: colophon – *Šumma ālu*, snakes tablet 22; *Freedman* 2006¹³¹. P. 67 – tablet 24. Sally Freedman comments that this is the variant numbering of the series. 708.

K. 2689: probably *Šumma ālu* (*Šumma ālu* year); 708.

K. 3070+7157+11830+12890(+3956): colophon – *Šumma ālu*; the tablet number is broken (sic!); *Freedman* 2006. P. 132b scorpion divination, *Šumma ālu* tablet 30 or 31; 708.

K. 3066: probably *Šumma ālu* (*Šumma ālu* year and colophon type); 707.

K. 3074+K. 11004: *Šumma ālu* 120; 707.

K. 3055+K. 12089+3075: colophon – *Šumma ālu* 45; *Guinan* 2002. P. 14, *Heefsel* 2002. P. 234¹³², and *Freedman* Academia.edu¹³³ – *Šumma ālu* 49; 707; Steven Lieberman's suggestion that K. 3075 is its join is correct (*Lieberman* 1987. P. 205).

BM 131656: *Šumma ālu* 84; 707.

K. 3064: probably *Šumma ālu* (*Šumma ālu* year and colophon type); 707.

K. 20700+K. 20730: *Šumma ālu*; 707.

K. 4125: colophon – *Šumma ālu*; *Guinan* 2002. P. 15 – sacrificial sheep behaviour; not dated.

Rm. 155: Prodigies of the Fall of Akkad; not dated.

Rm. 2, 286: Prodigies of the Fall of Akkad; not dated.

K. 2011+K. 6354+K. 3092+K. 10365: *Šumma ālu* x4–8 (?; last “4” preserved).

K. 6349: probably *Šumma ālu* (based on the colophon style, only the colophon survived).

K. 4097+Rm. 93+Rm. 544: colophon – *Šumma ālu*; *Guinan* 2002. P. 15, n. 42; 16 – excerpt tablet from *Šumma ālu* 91–94; *Freedman* 2006. P. 341–342 – incipits of tablets 91–95.

Oracle Questions (*tamītu*; not dated):

K. 2608+K. 2633+K. 3101b+K. 3435

Rm. 222+Rm. 513: *Koch* 2015¹³⁴. P. 69 – ornithoscopy, defined by W. G. Lambert as *ikribu*.

Numerology:

Esoteric Explanatory Series I.NAM.GIŠ.ĪUR.AN.KI.A (the only dated tablet is of 684)

K. 2670: I.NAM.GIŠ.ĪUR.AN.KI.A, third division; 684.

K. 170+Rm. 520: excerpt of I.NAM.GIŠ.ĪUR.AN.KI.A; not dated.

K. 2164+K. 2195+K. 3510: I.NAM.GIŠ.ĪUR.AN.KI.A, second division; not dated.

Rituals:

K. 3242+K. 5357+K. 6209+K. 6426+K. 6502+K. 9487+K. 9500+K. 9532+K. 10786+K. 10917+K. 11949: Ritual of an exorcist (*barû*); not dated.

Hemerology:

K. 98+MS 2226: a tablet of favourable days (*Ūmū tābūtu*) with excerpts from *Iqqur ipuš* and *Šumma ālu*. Date broken off(?), 709-708(?).

Appendix 2

Catalogue of Double and Triple Dated Colophons and Date Formulas and Dates by the Royal Year Only

All the colophons have been collated using the photographs published on the CDLI site and then the colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu were additionally collated at the British Museum unless otherwise is noted. Edition is quoted if there is one, but the editions and restorations below are not necessarily identical with the previous ones. All Rawlinson's copies (III R) referred to here contain only colophons. Underlined are parts of the texts, which appear in the handcopies but either are not on the tablet anymore, or were restored already in the handcopy.

All the restorations of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's colophons rely on the closest parallels. There is not a single complete colophon of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu that terminates with a *limmu* date. Thus it can be assumed that all his dated colophons were double or triple dated. Since there is not a single tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu dated to 716–710 and 704–684, where the regnal year of Sargon or Sennacherib as the kings of Assyria is not attested unless broken, all the colophons of these years have been restored as double dated. Between 709–705, all the colophons have triple dates or their traces unless completely broken. Based on this, the broken off colophons of this period with the traces of a date are restored as triple dated. In all Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's colophons from the reign of Sargon, *arkû* follows the royal name unless broken. If there are orthographical variations, but the restoration is clear, nominalization is used instead of transliteration.

Dates are in accordance with Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's system, that is 721, ascension of Sargon and 704 ascension of Sennacherib; 709 the first year of Sargon as the king of Babylon. The cases of deviation are marked.

Double dates of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu and others:

A. Nabû-zuqup-kēnu

716

1. Museum number: K. 2686+2687

Copy: AAT 29; III R 2, 1

BAK 293A

Year: 716

Text type: *EAE* 36 in the colophon, *EAE* 33 (Reiner 1998. P. 234)

Notes: not collated at the Museum.

Rev.

- 6' DIŠ *ina* ^{iti}DU₆ UD 10.KÁM 20 K[AN₄ ...]
 7' DUB 36.KÁM UD AN ^{d+}*En-lil ki-i pi-i* ^{giš}LE.U₅.UM GABA.RI KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki} SAR-*ma* BA.AN.È
 8' ^r*tup-pi* ^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.[NA] DUMU ^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*šú* ^{lu}DUB.SAR-*r[š]*
 9' ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^m*Gab-bu*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*— [KAM]-*eš* ^{lu}GAL DUB.SAR^{mes} ^{uru}*Ka-lāb* ^{iti}SIG₄ UD 29.KÁM
 10' [*li-mu* ^mDÜG.]GA—GIŠ.MI—É.ŠĀR.RA ^{lu}GAR.KUR ^{uru}ŠĀ. URU⁷ MU 6.KÁM ^mLUGAL—*ú-kin* EGIR-^r*ú*
 LUGAL KUR AN.ŠĀR^{ki}

Rev.

- 6' If in month Tašritu on the 10th day the Sun is ecli[psed...],
 7' 36th tablet (of) *Enūma Anu Enlil*. Written and collated in accordance with the wooden board, an original from Babylon.
 8' A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kē[nu], son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
 9' descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēr[eš], the chief of the scribes. Kalḫu, Simānu, 29th day,
 10' [eponymy of Tā]b-šil-Ešarra, governor of Assur, 6th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria.

2. Museum number: K. 3129

Copy: AAT 47a; ACh Ishtar 37

BAK 293K but in fact not 293 type (^mLUGAL-*ú-kin* [297A–C; K. 2690] and LÚ.A.BA [293L, N; 294U; 302])

Year: 716

Text type: *EAE* 63 in the colophon, *EAE* 64 (?; Reiner 1998. P. 227)

- 6' [...DU]B 60+*šu* 3.KÁM UD AN ^{d+}*En-lil ki-i pi*... *šaṭirma* BA.AN.È *tup-pi* ^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.[NA]
 7' [DUMU ^{md}AMAR.]UTU—MU—BA-*šú* ^{lu}A.BA ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^m*Gab-bi*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*¹—KA[M-*eš* ^{lu}GAL *tupšarri*
^{uru}*Kalab* ^{iti}X UD Y.KÁM]
 8' [*li-mu* ^mDÜG.GA—GIŠ.MI—É.ŠĀR.RA ^{lu}GAR.KUR ^uruŠĀ.URU MU 6.KÁM* ^mLUGAL—*ú-kin* EGIR-[*ú*
 LUGAL KUR *Aššum*^{ki}]

- 6' 63rd [...tab]let (of) *Enūma Anu Enlil*. Written and collated in accordance with.... A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu],
 7' [son of Marduk]-šumu-iqīša, the scribe, descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēr[eš], the chief of the scribes. Kalḫu, month X, Yth day],
 8' [eponymy of Tāb-šil-Ešarra, governor of] Assur, 6th year, Sargon the Seco[nd, king of Assyria].

3. Museum number: 1891, 5-9 Bu, 97

Copy: AAT 35a

BAK 293I

Year: 716

Text type: *EAE* 41

Notes: not collated at the Museum.

4' [DIŠ...IM.]DIRI UGU-šú i-š[u ...]

ruling

5' [...IGI.]BAR-*ma mu-še-lu-ú* GAR-*a*[*n*...]

6' [DUB] 41.KÁM UD AN⁷ <^d>*En-líl ki-i pi-i*[...*šaṭirma* BA.AN.È]

7' [*tup-pi*]^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA DUMU [^{md}AMAR. UTU—MU—BA-šá *tupšar(r)*]

8' [ŠÁ.BA]L.BAL^m *Gab-bu*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*-KAM⁷—*eš*^{liú}[GAL *tupšarri*^{uru} *Kalah*ⁱⁱX UD Y.KÁM]

9' [*li-mu*]^{md}DÜG.GA—GIŠ.MI—É.ŠÁR.RA^{liú}GAR.KUR^{uru}ŠÁ.URU [...]

10' [MU 6.KÁM^mLUGAL-*ú-kin* EGIR-*ú* LUGAL KUR *Aššur*^{ki}]

4' [If...a clo]ud upon it...[...]

5' [...you ob]serve and a *cloud formation* stay[s...],

6' 41st tablet (of) *Enūma Anu Enlil*. [Written and collated] in accordance with [...].

7' [A tablet] of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, [son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe],

8' [descen]dant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the chi[ef of the scribes. Kalḫu, month X, Yth day],

9' [epo]nymy of Ṭāb-šil-Ešarra, the governor of Assur, [...]

10' [6th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria].

4. Museum number: K. 3067

Copy: III R 2, 2

Not in BAK

Year: 716

Notes: flake of a colophon.

1' [*tup-pi*]^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU⁷—[BA-šá *tupšar(r)*]

2' [ŠÁ.B]AL.BAL^m *Gab-bi*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM⁷-[*eš*^{liú}GAL *tupšarri*]

3' [^{uru}*Kalah*ⁱⁱX UD Y.KÁM *li-mu*]^{md}DÜG.]⁷GA—GIŠ.MI—É.ŠÁR.RA^{liú}GAR.KUR^{uru}[ŠÁ.URU]

4' [MU 6.KÁM^mLUGAL—*ú-kin* EGIR-*ú* LUGAL KUR *Aššur*^{ki}]

1' [A tablet of Nabû-zuqup]-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-[iqīša, the scribe],

2' [descen]dant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēr[eš, the chief of the scribes].

3' [Kalḫu, month X, Yth day, eponymy of Ṭā]b-šil-Ešarra, the governor of [Assur],

4' [6th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria].

712

5. Museum number: K. 2680

Copy: III R 2, 7

BAK 294U

Year: 712

Text type: *Šumma hašú*(?)

1' [*Šumma i-na* ... SAG]ŠU² MUR² [x (x)]⁷ x x⁷ DINGIR^{mes}

2' [DUB X.KAM^{uzum}]UR² I UŠ 55.ĀM MU ŠID.BLIM

3' [*ke-i pi*... *šaṭirma*] BA.AN.È

4' [*tup-pi*]^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-šá^{liú}A.BA

5' [ŠÁ.BAL.BAL^m *Gab-bi*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-]⁷*eš*^{liú}GAL>^{liú}A.BA^{mes}

6' [^{uru}*Kalah*ⁱⁱ]GAL UD 12.KAM

7' [*li-mu Šarru-emuranni*]^{liú}]⁷GAR.⁷KUR^{kur} *Lul-lu-mi-e*

- 8' [MU 10.KÁM ^mLUGAL—ú-kin] ᵀEGIR ᵀ-ú
 9' [LUGAL KUR ^dAš+šú]ᵀ^{ki}
- 1' [If on ...] the lung's ["tur]ban" [...] gods.
 2' [Xth tablet (of) the *Lung*; 115 lines.
 3' [Written (and)] collated [in accordance with...].
 4' [A tablet of Nabû-zuqub-kēnu, so]n of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
 5' [descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš], the chief of the scribes.
 6' [Kalḫu], Kislīmu, 12th day,
 7' [eponymy of Šarru-ēmuranni], governor of Lullumû,
 8' [10th year, Sargon] the Second,
 9' [king of Ass]yria.

711

6. Museum number: K. 2678

Copy: partly in III R 2, 5

BAK 297A

Year: 711

Text type: *Šumma hašû* (13; Koch 2005. P. 267)

- 3' [DIŠ *i-na* x (x) 1]5 SAGŠU MUR GİR GAR-*at*¹³⁵ ERÍN.NI [DINGIR]^{mes}-šú [...] ^{gr}
 4' [DUB X.]KAM ^{uz}MUR 1 UŠ 40.ÂM MU ŠID.BI[.IM]
 5' [*ki-i pi*]-ᵀ ^{gr}ᵀ^{gr}LE.U₅.UM LIBIR.RA ša ^mLÚ—^dIB-*li-ia* DUMU ^mÉ-*sag-il*—SUM ^{lu}[HAL]
 6' [^m]^dAG—*zu*-*qu-up*—GI.NA DUMU ^{md}*Ma-ru-duk*—MU—BA-šá ^{lu}DUB.SAR-*ri*
 7' ŠÀ.BAL.BAL ^m*Gab-bu*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-*es* ^rLU GAL ᵀ DUB.SAR^{mes} *a-na ta-mar-ti-šú ú-šá-ás-ᵀir-ma ib-ri*
 8' ^{uru}*Kal-lab*₄ ^{iti}KIN UD 25.KAM ᵀ *li* [^{md}]-*mu* ᵀNIN.ᵀURTA—*a-lik*—*pa-ni* ^{lu}GAR.KUR ^{uru}*Si*-*im-me-e*
 9' MU 11.KÁM ^{as}LUGAL—ú-kin¹³⁶ EGI[R-ú] LUGAL KUR ^dA-šur₄^{ki}

- 3' [If on ...the rig]ht of the lung's “turban” there is a “footmark”, his army, his [god]s
 4' [Xth tablet] (of) the *Lung*; 100 the number of its lines.
 5' [In accordan]ce with the wooden board, ancient original of Amēl-IB-līja¹³⁷, son of Esagil-iddina, the [diviner],
 6' [Na]bû-zuqub-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
 7' descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes, for his reading copied and collated.
 8' Kalḫu, Ulūlu, 25th day, epon[y]my] of Ninurta-ālik-pāni, governor of Si'immê,
 9' 11th year, Sargon the Seco[nd], king of Assyria.

7. Museum number: K. 2683+K. 8083

Copy: partly in III R 2, 6

BAK 297B

Year: 711

Text type: *Šumma hašû* (13; Koch 2005. P. 267)

- 16' [DIŠ *i-na* x (x) 1]5 SAGŠU MUR GİR GAR-*at* ERÍN.NI DINGIR^{mes}-šú [...]^{gr}ᵀTUKUL-šú
 17' [DUB X.k]AM ^{uz}MUR 1 UŠ 40.ÂM [MU] ŠID.BI.IM
 18' [*ki-i pi-i*]-ᵀ ^{gr}LE.U₅.UM LIBIR.RA ᵀ ša ᵀ ^mLÚ ᵀ—^dIB-*li-ia* DUMU ^mÉ-*sag-il*—SUM ᵀ ^{lu}[HAL]
 19' [^{md}]^dAG—*zu-q*]-*u-up*—GI.NA DUMU ^{md}[*Ma*]-*ru-duk*—MU—BA ᵀ-šá ^rLU ᵀ DUB.SAR-*ri*

- 20' [ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^mGab-bu-DINGIR^{mes}-ni]-KAM-eš [lú.GAL D]UB.SAR^{mes} ^ra-na ta-mar-ti^r-[šú ú-šá]-^rás^r-^rir-ma
ib-ri^(sic)
- 21' [^{uru}Kāl-lab₄ ^{iti}X UD Y.KAM li-mu ^{md}NIN.]URTA—^alik—^{pa}ni ^{lu}GAR.KUR ^{uru}[Si²]-^rim-me-e^r
- 22' [MU 11.KAM ^mLUGAL—^úkin EGIR-ú] LUGAL KUR ^dA-šur^{ki}
- 16' [If on ...the rig]ht of the lung's “turban” there is a “footmark”, his army, his gods [...] his
weapon.
- 17' [Xth tablet] (of) the *Lung*; 100 the number of its lines.
- 18' [In accordance] with the wooden board, ancient original of Amēl-IB-līja, son of
Esagil-iddina, the diviner,
- 19' [Nabû-zuq]up-kēnu, son of [Ma]rduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
- 20' [descendant of Gabbi-ilān]i-ēreš, [the chief of the sc]ribes, for his reading [co]pied and
collated.
- 21' [Kal]ḫu, month X, Yth day, eponymy of Nin]urta-ālik-pāni, governor of [Si']immê,
- 22' [11th year, Sargon the Second], king of Assy[ria].

8. Museum number: K. 2692+K 3164

BAK 297C

Year: 711

Text type: *Šumma hašú* 3

- 6' [BE GÍR GIM ^{gi}ŠBAN²¹³⁸ ^{gis}TUKUL šá GAB² ina UD SUD-^{qá} [...]
- 7' DUB 3²[.KAM ^{uzu}]“MUR” 1 UŠ 17.ĀM MU ŠID.[BI.IM]
- 8' *ki-i* KA [^{gis}ŠLE.]U₅ LIBIR.RA ša ^mLÚ—^dIB-*li-ia* [DUMU ^mÉ-sag-*il*—SUM ^{lu}]HAL
- 9' ^{md}AG—^{zu}-^rqub—GIN^r DUMU ^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-šá ^{lu}DUB.SAR ŠĀ. B[AL.BAL
^mGab-bu—DINGIR^{mes}-ni—KAM-eš^{lu}]^r GAL DUB.SAR^{mes}
- 10' *a-na ta-mar-ti^r-šú ú-šá-ás-ir-ma^r ib-ri^{uru} Kāl^r-lab₄^{iti}KIN.^d[INNIN.NA UD X.]KAM*
- 11' *li-mu^{md} NIN.URTA—^a-lik—^{pa}ni^{lu}GAR.[KUR] ^{uru}Si²-im-me-e^r MU 11.^rKĀM^r [^mLUGAL-^úkin EGIR-^ú
LUGAL] KUR ^dAš+šur^{ki}*
- 6' [If the Path is like] a bow (and) a Weapon of the left, on a distant day [...].
- 7' 3[X]rd tablet (of) the *Lung*; 77 the number of its lines.
- 8' In accordance with the wooden board, ancient original of Amēl-IB-līja, [son of
Esaggil-iddina, the] diviner,
- 9' Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe, desc[endant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš,
the] chief of the scribes,
- 10' for his reading copied and collated. Kalḫu, Ulūlu, Xth day,
- 11' eponymy of Ninurta-ālik-pāni, gove[rnor of] Si'immê, 11th year, [Sargon the Second, king
of] Assyria.

9. Museum number: K. 8014

Copy: CT 30 28

Edition: Koch 2005. P. 253–267

Not in BAK, 297C type

Year: 711

Text type: Koch 2005. P. 253–267: commentary to *multābiltu* 4; CCP: <http://ccp.yale.edu/P397438> – commentary to *multābiltu* 14–15, 8–9

Rev.

- 9' [BE UR₅.ÚŠ^{mes}-ka] 15 ZI^{mes} [x x]
 10' [x x x x x x x x] *ke-i* KA ⁸⁵LE.U₅.UM [x x]
 11' [^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA DU]MU ^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-šá [*tupšar(r)*]
 12' [ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^mGab-bu—DINGIR^{mes}-ni—KAM-eš^{lú}] GAL DUB.SAR^{7mes} *a-na ta-mar-ti-šú ú-šá-ás-ṭir-ma*
ib-ri
 13' [^{uru}Kál-lab₄ ^{iti}X UD Y.KAM *li-mu* ^{md}NIN.URTA—*a-lik—p*]a-ni ^{lú}GAR.KUR [^{uru}Si'-im-me-e]
 14' [MU 11.KĀM ^mLUGAL]—ú-[*kin* EGIR-ú LUGAL KUR *Aššur^{ki}*]

Rev.

- 9' [If your liver] on the right openings [...]
 10' [...] in accordance with a wooden board [...]
 11' [Nabû-zuqap-kēnu, s]on of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, [the scribe],
 12' [descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the ch]ief of the scribes, for his reading co[pi]ed and
 collated].
 13' [Kalḫu, month X, Yth day, eponymy of Ninurta-ālik-p]āni, governor of [Si'immē],
 14' [11th year, Sar]go[n the Second, king of Assyria].

704

10. Museum number: K. 3068
 Copy: CT 30 25; III R 2, 17
 Edition: Koch-Westenholz 2000. P. 139–150
 BAK 294B
 Year: 704
 Text type: *manzāzu*-commentary 1

Rev.

- 1' x x [...]
 2' [*tup-pi* ^{md}A]G—*zu-qu-up*—^rGI.NA DUMU ^{md}AMAR.⁷UTU—MU—BA-šá ^rlúDUB.SAR⁷
 3' [ŠĀ.BAL.BAL] ^mGab⁷-bi—DINGIR^{mes}-ni—KAM-eš^{lú} GAL DUB.SAR^{mes} ^{uru}Kal-ḫa ^{iti}ŠE UD 22.KĀM
 4' [*li-mu* ^{md}A]G—*di-ni*—DÛ-uš^{lú}GAR.KUR ^{uru}NINA^{ki}
 5' [MU 1.KĀM ^{md}]EN.ZU—ŠEŠ^{mes}—*eri*ⁿ-ba LUGAL KUR ^dAššur^{ki}

Rev.

- 2' [A tablet of N]abû-zuqap-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
 3' [descendant of] Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes. Kalḫu, Addaru, 22nd day,
 4' [eponymy of Na]bû-dēni-ēpuš, governor of Nineveh,
 5' [1st year], Sennacherib, king of Assyria.

701

11. Museum number: Sm. 1003
 BAK 294T
 Year: 701
 Notes: a flake of a colophon.

- 1' x x x [...]'x.x'

- 2' [tup-pi^{md}AG—zu-qu-up—GL.NA] r DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA⁷-šá^{lí}DUB.SAR
 3' [ŠÁ.BAL.BAL^mGab-bi—DINGIR^{mes}-ni—KAM-eš^{lí}GAL] DUB.SAR^{mes}
 4' [uru^uKalab^{iti}X UD Y.KÁM lî]-r mu^mHja-na⁷-an-nu^[li]GAR. r KUR⁷ uru^u[Til]-bar-si-íp
 5' [MU 4.KÁM^{md}] r EN.ZU—ŠEŠ^{7mes}—r eri⁷-ba LUGAL r KUR^dAš+šur^{ki}

- 2' [A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu], son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
 3' [descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief] of the scribes.
 4' [Kalḫu, month X, Yth day, epony]my of Hjanānu, governor of [Til] Barsip,
 5' [4th year], Sennacherib, king of Assyria.

12. Museum number: K. 3163

Copy: AAT 73d; ACh Sin 16; III R 2, 18

Edition: *Fincke* 2014. P. 131

BAK 293M

Year: 701

Text type: *rikis gerri* of *EAE*; one of the first four tablets of *rikis gerri* (*Fincke* 2014. P. 132)

Notes: should be restored as double dated.

- 9' [DIŠ x x x (x)] di-ḫu u di-lip-ti ina KUR GÁL-š[i...]¹³⁹
 10' [DUB X.KÁM] ri-kiš KASKAL^{II} UD AN [^{d+}En-lil...]
 11' [ke-i pi]-i^{gš}LE.U⁵.UM^{gš}ŠUR.MÎN GABA[.RI KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki2} šatirma BA.AN.È]
 12' [tup-]pi^{md}AG—zu-qu-up—GL.NA DUMU^m[^dAMAR.UTU—MU—BA-šá tupšar(r)]
 13' [ŠÁ.B]AL.BAL^mGab-bi—DINGIR^{mes}-ni—KAM-eš^{lí}[^uGAL tupšarr^{uru}Kalab^{iti}X UD Y.KÁM]
 14' [lî]-mu^mHja-na-nu^{lí}GAR.KUR^{ur}[^vTil-bar-si-íp]
 15' [MU 4.KÁM^{md}EN.ZU—ŠEŠ^{mes}—eri-ba LUGAL KUR Aššur^{ki}]

- 9' [If...] diḫu-disease and insomnia will occur in the land [...].
 10' [Xth tablet] (of) the *rikis gerri* *Enūma Anu* [*Enlil*...]
 11' [Written (and) collated in accordance with] the wooden board of cypress, origin[al from Babylon].
 12' [A ta]blet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of [Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe],
 13' [descen]dant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, [the chief of the scribes. Kalḫu, month X, Yth day],
 14' [epon]ymy of Hjanānu, governor of [Til Barsip],
 15' [4th year, Sennacherib, king of Assyria].

698

13. Museum number: K. 398

Copy: ACh Suppl. 2, Ishtar 77

BAK 293P

Year: 698

Text type: *EAE* 56, commentary (*Reiner* 1998. P. 217)

Notes: the underlined end of line 6 is according to *Millard* 1994¹⁴⁰. P. 122. Year of Sennacherib's ascension is 704 according to this colophon.

- 11 DIŠ^dUDU.IDIM DIRI NU HUŠ UN^{mes} [...]
 ruling

12 *šá šà* ^dUDU.IDIM *pi-i*[-*sá*...]

ruling

13 *ki-i pi-i* ^{gis}LE.U₅.UM ^{gis} ... *šařirma* BA.AN.È]

Rev.

1 IM.GÍD.DA ^{md}AG—*zu-q*[*u-up*—GI.NA...]

2 DUMU ^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*šá* [*tuššar(r)*]

3 ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^m*Gab-bi*—D[INGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-*eš* ^{lú}GAL *tuššarr*]

4 ^{uru}*Kal-ḫa* ^{iti}GAN [UD X.KÁM...]

5 *li-mu* ^m*Šu-lum*-[*šarri* ^{lú}GAR.KUR ^{uru}*Ḫalzi-atbāri*]

6 MU 7.KÁM ^{md}EN.ZU[—ŠEŠ^{mes}—*eri-ba*] LUGAL KUR ^d*Aš+šur*^{ki}

11 If a planet is enlarged (*atartu*)/is full (*malû*)¹⁴¹ no fury people [...]

12 *A divi[sion]* of inside the planet [...]

13 [Written and collated] in accordance with the wooden board of [...-wo]od.

Rev.

1 A long tablet of Nabû-zuq[up-kēnu ...],

2 son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, [the scribe],

3 descendant of Gabbi-il[āni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes].

4 Kalḫu, Kislīmu, [Xth day ...],

5 eponymy of Šulmu-šarri, governor of Ḫalzi-atbāri],

6 7th year, Senn[acherib], king of Assyria.

694

14. Museum number: K. 75+K. 237

BAK 305

Year: 694

Text type: commentary on *EAE* 5 (?)

Notes: landscape tablet, written in Babylonian ductus. Year of Sennacherib's ascension is 704 according to this colophon.

Rev.

20 *ki-i* ^rKA ^r[^{gis}LE.U₅.UM TIN.]^rTIR ^{ki}*šá* ^{md+}AG—URÚ-*ir* DUMU ^{md}*É-a*—*pat-ta-ni* ^{lú}TIN.TIR^{ki-i}

21 *a-na ta-mar-ti-šú is-^rsu-ḫa* AB. ^rSAR.ĀM BA.AN.È *tuš-pi* ^{md+}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA DUMU ^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*šá* ^{lú}DUB.SAR

22 ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^m*Gab-bi*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-*eš* ^{lú}GAL DUB.SAR^{mes} ^{uru}*Ka-lāḫ* ^{iti}ŠE.KIN.KU₅ UD 23.KÁM

23 *li-mu* ^{md}DINGIR—KI-*ia* ^{lú}GAR.KUR ^{uru}*Šá-i-me-ri-šú* ^ùMU 11.KÁM ^{d+}EN.ZU—ŠEŠ^{mes}—*eri-ba* LUGAL KUR *Aš+šur*^{ki}

Rev.

20 In accordance with [the wooden tablet from Baby]lon of Nabû-nāšir, son of Ea-pattāni, the Babylonian.

21 For his reading excerpted, copied (and) collated, a tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,

22 descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes. Kalḫu, Addaru, 23rd day,

23 eponymy of Ilu-ittija, governor of Damascus, and 11th year, Sennacherib, king of Assyria.

686

15. Museum number: K. 14169

Copy: AAT 43a

Edition: *Koch* 2005. P. 253–267

Not in BAK

Year: 686

Text type: *EAE* 57 (?; *Reiner* 1998. P. 266)1' DIŠ^{mulU}[GA^{142mušen} ...]

2' 'x' [...]

Rev.

1' [*tup-pi*]^{rmd}[AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*ša* *tupšar(r)*]2' [ŠÀ.]BAL.BAL^m *Gab*^r—[*bu/i*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-eš^{li}GAL *tupšarr*]3' ^{uru}*Kal-ba* ^riti^{AB}^r[UD X.KÁM *li-mu* ...]4' MU 19.KÁM^{md}[EN.ZU—ŠEŠ^{mes}—*eri-ba* LUGAL *Aššur*^{ki}]

1' If Co[rvus ...]

2' ...

Rev.

1' [A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe],

2' [de]scendant of Gab[bi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes].

3' Kalḫu, Tebētu, [Xth day, eponymy of ...],

4' 19th year, [Sennacherib, king of Assyria].

684

16. Museum number: K. 2670

Copy: III R 2, 22

Edition: *Livingstone* 1986¹⁴³. P. 28–29

BAK 299

Year: 684

Notes: Millard dates this eponym to 684. If so, the year of Sennacherib's ascension would be 705 according to this colophon. Apparently there is a mistake in the last date of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu.

1' 1/DIŠ MU[L² ...]

2' 1/DIŠ MUL [...]

3' 1 'GURUN x 30' *aš-šu* [...]4' 3-*šu* *pīr-su* I.NAM.GIŠ.HUR.A[N.KI.A *tab-ba-a-ti* AN-e u KI-ti]5' *šu-ut ap-si-i ma-la ba-áš-mu* I[M.GÍD.DA A.RA-e *tup-pi*]6' ^{md}AG—*zu-qu-p*—GI.NA DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*ša*^{li}DUB.SAR7' ^{li}M[*AŠ*².*MAŠ*²]8' *a-na ta-mar-ti* ^{md}MUŠ—MU—KAM-eš DUMU-*ia ul-tu* 1 ½ MU.AN.NA9' *dī-ig-la ú-ka-b-bir-ma zu-mar ú-ba-ab-bi-iš-ma ab-r[i]*10' *a-mi-ru la i-ia-ap-pil* ^{iti}AB UD 30.KÁM *li-mu* ^m*Ma-zu-a*[*r-ne-e*]11' ^{li}GAR.KUR ^{uru}*Kul-la*—[*ni-i*]

- 12' MU 22.KÁM ^{md}EN.ZU—šEŠ^{mes}—*eri-ba* LUGAL KUR ^dAš[+šur^{ki}]
- 1' One star / if a sta[r ...]
- 2' One star / if a star [...]
- 3' “Fruit” ... is Šîn because [...]
- 4' 3rd division (of) I.NAM.GIŠ.HUR.A[N.KI.A, *pairs of corresponding things*¹⁴⁴ of heaven and earth]
- 5' that of the Apsû, as many as there are. [A long mathematical tablet of]
- 6' Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
- 7' the exorcist,
- 8' for the perusal of Issār-šumu-ēreš, my “son”, after 1 ½ years,
- 9' I strained my eyesight, quickly *excerpted/summarized* (and) checke[d].
- 10' The reader must not disrespect (it). Tebētu, 30th day, eponymy of Maza[rnê],
- 11' governor of Kulla[ni],
- 12' 22nd year, Sennacherib, king of Assyria.

No date preserved

17. Museum number: K. 14971

Not in BAK

Notes: was at least double dated.

Rev.

- 1' [^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA] ṽDUMU⁷ ^{md}AMAR.UTU—ṽMU⁷—[BA-šá *tuššarrz*]
- 2' ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^mGab-bi—[DINGIR^{mes}—*ni*—KAM-eš^{lú}GAL *tuššarrz*]
- 3' ^{uru}Kal-ḫa ⁱⁱⁱ[X UD Y.KÁM *li-mu*...]
- 4' [MU Z.KÁM ^mPN LUGAL KUR Aššur^{ki}]¹⁴⁵

Rev.

- 1' [Nabû-zuqup-kēnu], son of Marduk-šumu-iqī[ša, the scribe],
- 2' descendant of Gabbi-[ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes].
- 3' Kalḫu, month [X, Yth day, eponymy of...],
- 4' [Zth year, PN, king of Assyria].

18. Museum number: Sm. 2090

Not in BAK

Year: 701(?)

Notes: was at least double dated. No date preserved; no eponym of Sargon or Sennacherib with a name ending with sign I is known. The most probable candidate is Manzarnê, the eponym of 684, whose Phoenician name was most often misspelled by Assyrians. However, such a restoration of the date is not realized because of its high uncertainty.

- 1' [ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^mGab-bu/i—DINGIR^{mes}—*ni*—KAM-eš^{lú}GAL DUB.SAR^{mes}]
- 2' [x x x x x (x) ^{uru}Kalabⁱⁱⁱ] ṽAB²⁷ UD 12.KAM
- 3' [*li-mu* x x x x x x x (x)]-i ^{lú}GAR.KUR ^{uru}[...]
- 4' [...LU]GAL KUR Aššur^{ki}]

- 1' [descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš], the chief of the scribes.

- 2' [...Kalḫu], Tebētu, 12th day,
 3' [eponymy of ...], governor of [...],
 4' [...k]ing of Assyria.

19. Museum number: K. 6346+K. 15766

BAK 294L

Notes: should be double or triple dated.

- 1' [...]ᵀ x x x x xᵀ [...]
 2' [... AB.SAR.]ĀM BA.AN[.È]
 3' [tuḫ-pi^dAG—zu-qu-ḫ—GI.NA] DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-šá^{lú}DUB.ᵀ SARᵀ
 4' [šĀ.BAL.BAL^mGab-bi—DINGIR^{mes}-ni—KAM-eš^rlú<GAL>] DUB.SAR^{mes}
 5' [ᵀ^{ru}KalabⁱX UD Y li-mu...]^rlúᵀGAR.[KUR...]
 1' [...]
 2' [...writ]ten (and) collat[ed].
 3' [Tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu], son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
 4' [descendant of Gabbī-ilāni-ēreš, the chief] of the scribes.
 5' [Kalḫu, month X, Yth day, eponymy of...], governor [of ...].

B. Others

716

20. Inūrta-ubalissu

Museum number: VAT 8807

Copy: Lambert 1960¹⁴⁶. Pls. 55–57

Edition: Lambert 1960. P. 213–220

BAK 313

Year: 716

Text type: literary, Popular Sayings

Notes: not collated; according to Lambert's handcopy. Colophon of the same type as Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's BAK 294, but the author is different. However, Nabû-zuqup-kēnu has LUGAL—GI.NA only starting with 709 and his 716 colophon has KUR AN.ŠÁR^{ki} (see no. 1). Note that here the patronymic is missing. The tablet comes from Assur.

- 29 [L]BIR.RA.BI.GIM AB.SAR BA.AN.È
 30 tuḫ-pi^{md}NIN.URTA—ú-bal-lit-su^{lú}A.BA
 31 šĀ.BAL.BAL^mGab-bi—DINGIR^{mes}-ni—KAM-eš^rlú<GAL> ᵀDUB.SAR^{mes}
 32 ᵀxᵀ [x x] ⁱⁱrXᵀ [...]
 33 [li]-mu^{md}DUG.GĀ—GI[š.M]I—É.ŠÁR.RA^{lú}GAR.KUR^{ru}šĀ.URU
 34 MU 6.KÁM^mLUGAL—GI.NA EGIR-ú LUGAL KUR Aš+šur^{ki}
 29 Writen (and) collated in accordance with the ancient [original].
 30 A tablet of Inūrta-ubalissu, the scribe,
 31 descendant of Gabbī-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes.

- 32 [...] month X [...],
 33 [epo]nymy of ʿĀb-šil-Ešarra, governor of Assur,
 34 6th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria.

714

21. Zaia

Excavation and museum numbers: ND 1120 = IM 56880

Copy: *Wiseman* 1952¹⁴⁷. Pl. 23

Edition: *van Driel* 1969¹⁴⁸. P. 200–203; *Deller* 1981¹⁴⁹. P. 64–66; SAA 20 55

Year: 714

Text type: royal ritual. Described by Donald J. Wiseman and Jeremy A. Black as “the finely written account of royal ceremonies” (CTN 4. P. 1).

Notes: collated from the photograph. Wiseman notes (Ibid. P. 62): “this tablet and the letters addressed to the king are obviously the work of first-class scribes and the texts bear a marked resemblance to the best library tablets in the Kuyunjik collection”. Nonetheless, Sargon’s ascension year is 722 according to *Zaia*.

The royal ritual was written by *Zaia*, a hereditary scribe of the city Assur. The ritual took place in Assur, in the vicinity of Ešarra; the tablet was found at Kalḫu, ca. 10 m east of Burnt Palace, Room viii. Among the participants is Nabû-šallimšunu, a royal scribe and the author of the Sargon’s Letter to Aššur, who comes especially from Kalḫu on occasion of this ceremony.

Incipit

- 1 [...ina] ar-ši^m LUGAL—GI.NA MAN KUR Aš+šur^r ki⁷
 2 [ina] i-me^{md} INNIN—BĀD^{li} GAR.KUR ur^u LÍMMU-ḫa
 ruling

- 1 [...at the ti]me of Sargon, king of Assyria,
 2 [ep]onymy of Issār-dūri, governor of Arrapha.

Colophon, BAK 314

ruling

Rev.

- 15' [...] SAG ki LIBIR.RA ZI-ḫa

double ruling

- 16' [...Za-a¹-a]¹⁵⁰ li^u DUB.SAR URU DUMU^{md} BA.Ú—ŠEŠ—SUM-na KIMIN DUMU^m UD.20.KĀM-a-a KIMIN
 DUMU^m SUḪUŠ—^dPA KIMIN
 17' [DUMU m...] KIMIN DUMU^{md} AG—be-el—DINGIR KIMIN DUMU^m r ŠEŠ⁷—ri-ba^{li} DUB.SAR URU KIMIN
 18' [DUMU m...] ia¹⁷—A-šur KIMIN DUMU^{md} A-šur₄—ki-na¹-ni KIMIN DUMU^{md} 30—DUMU.UŠ—SUM-na
 KIMIN
 19' [DUMU m...] šá-kín—šū-me KIMIN DUMU^{md} MES-ka¹b-tu—ŠEŠ^{mes}-šū KIMIN PEŠ
 m Aš+šur—EN—DINGIR^{mes} KIMIN
 20' [DUMU m...] a KIMIN DUMU^{md} A-šur—id-na-ni^{li} DUB.SAR URU KIMIN
 21' [ŠĀ.BAL.]BAL ša^{md} E-tel—pi—Mar-duk^{li} DUB.SAR É tu^p-pa-a-ti
 22' [i^{li}AB.(BA.)]É¹⁵¹ UD 22.KAM li-mu^{md} INNIN-BĀD^{li} GAR.KUR ur^u LÍMMU-ḫa
 23' [MU.(AN.NA)] 9 ša^m LUGAL—GI.NA MAN KUR^d A-šur

Rev.

- 15' [...] head, excerpted according to the ancient original.
 16' [...Zaia], the scribe of the city, son of Bābu-aḥu-iddina, *ditto*, son of Ešrāiu, *ditto*, son of Ubru-Nabû
 17' [son of...] *ditto*, son of Nabû-bēl-ili, *ditto*, son of Aḥu-erība, the scribe of the city, *ditto*,
 18' [son of...]a-Aššūr, *ditto*, son of Aššūr-kīnani, *ditto*, son of Sīn-aplu-iddina, *ditto*,
 19' [son of...]šakin-šumu, *ditto*, son of Marduk-kabtu-aḥḥēšu, *ditto*, heir of Aššūr-bēl-ilāni¹⁵²,
ditto,
 20' [son of...]a, *ditto*, son of Aššūr-idnanni, the scribe of the city, *ditto*,
 21' [descen]dant of Etel-pī-Marduk, the scribe of the tablet house.
 22' [Ṭebē]tu, 22nd day, eponymy of Issār-dūri, governor of Arrapha,
 23' 9th [year], Sargon, king of Assyria.

713

22. Date formula

Museum number: K 1989+K 4467+83-1-18, 425+1891, 5-9 Bu, 193

Copy: ADD 660; ADD 714; ADD 809; NARGD 32 (pls. 20–21)

Edition: NARGD 32; SAA 12 19

Year: 713

Text type: Sargon's renewal of grant to provide offerings to Aššur

Rev.

- 28 NINA^{ki} iiiSIG₄ UD 5.KĀM *li-mu* md Aš+šur—ba-[ni^{li} GAR.KUR umKa]l-*bi* MU 9.KĀM mMAN—GIN MAN
 KUR Aš+šur^{ki}

Rev.

- 28 Nineveh, Simānu, 5th day, eponymy of Aššūr-bā[ni, governor of Ka]lḥu; 9th year, Sargon,
 king of Assyria.

711

23. Museum number: K. 2690

Copy: III R 2, 8

Not in BAK, 297 type (date and LUGAL-ú-*kin*)

Year: 711

Notes: a flake. Name of the scribe is broken off, probably an apprentice of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's circle.

- 1' x x x x
 2' iū²GAR².KUR uruTA [Si²-*im-me-e*]¹⁵³
 3' MU 11.KĀM mLUGAL—ú[-*kin* EGIR-ú LUGAL KUR Aššur^{ki}]
 2' governor of [Si²immê],
 3' 11th year, Sarg[on the Second, king of Assyria].

709

24. Date formula

Museum number: N III 3157

Copy: ADD 1141; TCL 9 58

Edition: SAA 6 31; *Radner* 1997¹⁵⁴. P. 19–23

Year: 709

Text type: a deed

Notes: not collated; according to the handcopy by Karen Radner. A deed of Nabû-kabti-ahhēšu, palace scribe of Sargon, who purchases from four sellers a huge estate, adjoining the road to Kalḫu and located in the territory of the town Burūqu. The tablet was found at Khorsabad.

According to this date formula, Sennacherib’s ascension year was 705.

Rev.

27b ⁱⁱⁱAPIN UD 13.KÁM *li-mu*

28 ^mMan-nu—*ki*—Aš+šur—ZU ^{li*}GAR.KUR ^{uru}Til-e

29 MU 12.KÁM ^mLUGAL—GI.NA LUGAL KUR Aš+šur^{ki}

Rev.

27b Araḫsamnu, 13th day, eponymy of

28 Mannu-kī-Aššūr-lē’i, governor of Tillē,

29 12th year, Sargon, king of Assyria.

700

25. Museum number: K 2856+(14 more fragments)

Edition: *Borger* 1973¹⁵⁵. P. 164–176

BAK 501

Year: 700

Text type: ritual of the consecration of a priest of Enlil

Notes: name and patronymic are broken. Apparently a son or a descendent of the royal exorcist, maybe of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu. Writings [...^{li}MU₇.]MU₇ for the “exorcist” and GIŠIMMAR for the “king” are elements of cryptography.

According to this colophon, Sennacherib’s ascension year was 705.

Not collated at the Museum.

Rev. vi

41 ÉN TÚG.DU₈.DU₈.BABBAR.RA ME.TE.NAM.DINGIR.RA

42 [GABA.RI] ^rKÁ.DINGIR.RA ^{ki}*ki-ma* SUMUN-šú SAR-ma [IG]I.KÁR

43 [...ŠÁMAN.]LÁ TUR

44 [...^{li}MU₇.]MU₇ LUGAL AŠ

45 [x]^{ki}ⁱⁱⁱGAN^r[...U]D 11.KÁM

46 [*li*]-mu ^mMi-tu-nu ^{li}[GAR.KUR KUR ^{uru}]I-sa-na

47 [MU] 6.KÁM ^dAN.ZU—ŠEŠ.ŠEŠ—^reri^r-ba

48 LUGAL(GIŠIMMAR)¹⁵⁶ KUR ^dAš+šur^{ki}

49 [N]IR.GÁL.ZU NU.TÉŠ ^dUR²

Rev. vi

41 Incantation “Pure *tapsu*-cloth, an attribute of the god”.

- 42 [Original] from Babylon. In accordance with the ancient original written and [co]llated.
 43 [...] young [appren]tice
 44 [...excor]cist of the king of Assyria
 45 [GN], Kislīmu, 11th day,
 46 [epo]nymy of Metūnu, g[overnor] of Isāna,
 6th [year], Sennacherib,
 48 king of Assyria.
 49 Trusting in you may not be put to shame, O Nabû!

690

26. Date formula

Museum number:

1. Walters Art Gallery no. 41,109

2. probably Catholic university of America, no number

Copy: *Grayson* 1963¹⁵⁷. Pls. 1–4Edition: *Grayson* 1963. P. 83–96; RINAP 3/2 230.

Year: 690

Text type: royal inscription

Notes: not collated; according to the handcopy and photograph in *Grayson* 1963. This inscription is known from two copies on stone tablets, one in Walters Art Gallery and the other used to be at the Catholic university of America.

According to this date formula, Sennacherib's ascension year was 703.

Rev.

126 [iⁱⁱAP]IN UD 25.KAM ṛ^{md}lim^{md}-mu^{md}AG—GIN—PAB^{li}EN.NAM^{uru}Sa-me-ri-na MU.AN.NA 14
^{md}30—PAP^{mcš}—SU MAN ŠÚ MAN KUR Aš+šur^{ki}

126 [Araḥ]samnu, 25th day, eponymy of Nabû-kēnu-ušur, governor of the city of Samaria,
 14th year, Sennacherib, king of the world, king of Assyria.

685

27. Date formula

Museum number: Ki 1904-10-9, 139+238+401+Ki 1904-10-9, 393+404

Edition: SAA 6 174

Year: 685

Text type: a deed

Notes: not collated; according to SAA 6 174; no handcopy or photograph available. A deed of a slave purchase. The persons involved in this deal are otherwise unknown.

According to this date formula, Sennacherib's ascension year was 705.

16e ina MU.AN.NA 21^{md}30—PAP^{mcš}—SU MAN KUR Aš+šur^{ki}
 s 1ⁱⁱŠEⁱ UD 20.KÁM ṛ[im-mu^{md} Aš+šur—KALA]Gⁱ—niⁱ-a-ni
 2 x [x x x] x [x x x] x

16e In year 21 of Sennacherib, king of Assyria,

s 1 Addaru, 20th day, ep[onymy of Aššūr-da²]inanni¹⁵⁸.

684

28. Date formula

Museum number: Rm. 167

Copy: ADD 230

Edition: SAA 6 177

Year: 684

Text type: a deed

Notes: Ulūlāiu, a royal bodyguard, (PNA 3/II. P. 1376 [no. 13 under this name]) purchases a family of slaves from Nabû-erība (otherwise unknown). Ulūlāiu is also known as a witness, together with other military officials, including two cohort commanders of the queen, on the deed of Mardû/Martu', cities' or villages' manager of the queen (SAA 6 90)¹⁵⁹. Note that SAA 6 90 is also double dated. Among the witnesses on SAA 6 177 are a cohort commander, two "third" men and three scribes.

According to this date formula, Sennacherib's ascension year was 705.

Rev.

16 ⁱⁱGUD UD 8.KAM *li-mu*17 ^mMan-*za-ar-ni-e* ^{lu}EN.NAM18 KUR *Kul-la-ni-a*19 MU 22.KĀM ^{md}30—PAB^{mes}—SU20 LUGAL KUR *Aš+šur*^{ki}

Rev.

16 Ajaru, 8th day, eponymy

17 of Manzarnê, governor

18 of Kullanīa,

19 22nd year, Sennacherib,

20 king of Assyria.

683

29. Date formula

Museum number: 82-5-22, 34

Copy: ADD 447

Edition: SAA 6 90

Year: 683

Text type: a deed

Notes: not collated; according to the handcopies in ADD 447 and SAA 6 90.

A deed of Aḫi-ṭalli. A female administrator (*šakintu*) at Nineveh buys 17 slaves and an orchard from Martu', cities' or villages' manager of the queen, probably identical with Mardû in SAA 6 164, and a certain Mardû¹⁶⁰. Among the witnesses are two scribes and a chariot fighter. Nabû-šumu-iddina is the first witness.

According to this formula, Sennacherib's ascension year was 705.

16 ⁱⁱGUD UD 1.KĀM MU 23 ^{md}30—PAB^{mes}—SU17 MAN KUR *Aš+šur*^{ki} *lim-me* ^{md}Man-nu-*ki*—10—MAN[!]

- 18 [š]á^{uru} Šu-pi-te
 16 Ajaru, 1st day, 23rd year, Sennacherib,
 17 king of Assyria, eponymy of Mannu-kī-Adad-milki
 18 [o]f Šūpat.

676

30. Date formula
 Museum number: 83-1-18, 269
 Copy: ADD 502
 Edition: SAA 6 212
 Year: 676
 Text type: a deed

Notes: not collated; according to the handcopies in ADD 502 and SAA 6 212.

A deed of Mannu-kī-Arbail, a cohort commander, subsequently a charioteer. On the other two of his deeds the expression “in the time” (*ina tarṣi*) of Esarhaddon appears together with the *limmu* dates (SAA 6 201, 680; SAA 6 210, also 676). Nabû-šumu-iddina, a royal astrologer, is the tablet keeper.

Rev.

- 6 [i^{hi}BÁ]RA UD 25.KÁM 5.KÁM¹ MU.AN.[NA]
 7 [m^hAš+šur—p]AB—SUM—na MAN KUR AN.ŠÁ[R^{ki}]
 8 [lim-mu] m^hBan-b[a-a] i^{hi}SUKKAL 2-u]

Rev.

- 6 [Nis]annu, 25th day, 5th yea[r],
 7 [Esarh]addon, king of Assyri[a],
 8 [eponymy] of Banb[á, the second vizier].

Triple Dated Colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu:

709

31. Museum number: K. 5280
 Copy: AAT 12a; ACh Sin 15
 Edition: *Fincke* 2014. P. 132
 BAK 293C
 Year: 709
 Text type: tablet 6 of *rikiš gerri* of *EAE*
 Notes: should be restored as triple dated.

Rev.

- 3' [DIŠ ina] r^{hi}BARA₂ AN.MI 20 GAR-un ina MU.BI LUGAL [Úš-ma KUR ŠÁ HUL IGI SIG₅ IGI]¹⁶¹
 4' DUB 6.KÁM ri-kis ger-ri UD AN d⁺En-lil ki-[i pī x x šaiir(má)] r^hBA.AN.È'
 5' [š]up-pi md^{AG}—zu-qu-up—GI.NA DUMU m^d[AMAR.UTU]—MU—BA-ŠÁ [i^{hi}DUB.SAR]
 6' ŠÁ.BAL.BAL m^hGab-bi—DINGIR^{meš}-ni—KAM-eš^r i^{hi}GAL⁷ DUB.SAR^{meš} uruKal-ḫa i^{hi}X UD Y.KÁM]

- 7' *li-mu* ^mMan-nu—*ki*—^dAš+šur—^rZU⁷[X X X ^{li}]GAR.KUR ^{uru}Til-[*le-e*]
 8' [M]U 1[3.KÁ]M ^rLUGAL⁷—G[^l.NA EGIR-^ú LUGAL KUR Aššur^{ki}]
 9' [(^ú) MU 1.KÁM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

Rev.

- 3' [If in] Nisannu a solar eclipse takes place, in the same year the king will [die and a country that has experienced misfortune will experience good luck].
 4' 6th tablet (of) the *rikis gerri Enūma Anu Enlil*. [Written (and) col]lated in accorda[n]ce with ...].
 5' [A ta]blet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of [Marduk]-šumu-iqīša, [the scribe],
 6' descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes. Kalḫu, [month X, Yth day],
 7' eponymy of Mannu-kī-Aššūr-lē'i, [go]vernor of Til[lē],
 8' 1[3]th [y]ear, Sar[gon the Second, king of Assyria]
 9' [and 1st year, king of Babylon].

32. Museum number: K. 2688, BM 38296

Copy: AAT 14b; III R 2, 9

Edition: *Rochberg-Halton* 1988¹⁶². P. 119–120

BAK 293F

Year: 709

Text type: *EAE* 17

Notes: should be restored as triple dated.

- 1' ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^mGab-[*bi*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-*eš tupšar(r)* ^{uru}Kal-*ḫa* ⁱⁱⁱX UD Y.KÁM]
 2' *li-mu* ^mMan-nu—*ki*—^dAš+^ršur⁷—[ZU ^{li}GAR.KUR ^{uru}Til-*le-e*]
 3' MU 13.KÁM ^mLUGAL—GI.NA ^rEGIR⁷-^úLUGAL KUR Aššur^{ki} (^ú) MU 1.KÁM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

- 1' Descendant of Gab[bi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes. Kalḫu, month X, Yth day],
 2' eponymy of Mannu-kī-Aššūr-[lē'i, the governor of Tillē],
 3' 13th year, Sargon the Secon[d, king of Assyria, and 1st year, king of Babylon].

33. Museum number: K. 5277

Not in BAK

Year: 709

Text type: *EAE* 53 (*Reiner* 1998. P. 233); commentary on *EAE* 52 or 53 (CCP 3.1.52.C.a [http://ccp.yale.edu/P395970])

Rev.

- 1' [... *ki-i pi* ... *šatir(ma)*] ^rBA.⁷AN.È
 2' [*tup-pi* ^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA DUMU ^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*šá* ^{li}DUB.SAR ŠĀ.BAL.BAL
^mGab-*bi*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM]-*eš* ^{li}GAL DUB.SAR^{mes}
 3' [^{uru}Kal-*ḫa* ⁱⁱⁱX UD Y.KÁM *li-mu* ^mMan-nu—*ki*—^dAš+šur—ZU ^{li}GAR.KUR ^{uru}Til-*le-e*
 4' [MU 13.KAM ^mLUGAL—GI.NA EGIR-^ú LUGAL KUR Aššur^{ki} ^rki ^ú MU 1.KÁM LUGAL⁷ KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

Rev.

- 1' [Written (and)] collated [according to ...].
 2' [A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe, descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēr]eš, the chief of the scribes,

- 3' [Kalḫu, month X, Yth day, eponymy of Mannu-kī-Aššūr-lē'i, governor of Tjillê,
4' [13th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria, and 1st year, king of Babylon.

34. Museum number: DT 318

Not in BAK

Year: 709

Text type: Catalogue of omen incipits (*Oppenheim* 1974. P. 208, n. 45 with the reference to Hermann Hunger's identification as Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's [?])

Rev.

- 1' ^{uru}Kal-ḫa^{iti}X UD Y.KÁM li-mu^mMan-nu—ki—^dAššur—ZU^{lu}GAR.KUR ^{uru}Til-le-e]
2' ^rMU⁷ 13.KAM ^m[LUGAL—GI.NA EGIR-ú LUGAL KUR Aššur^{ki}]
3' ù MU 1.[KÁM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

Rev.

- 1' Kalḫu, month X, Yth day, eponymy of Mannu-kī-Aššūr-lē'i, the governor of Tillê],
2' 13th year, [Sargon the Second, king of Assyria],
3' and 1st year, [king of Babylon].

708

35. Museum number: K. 2682+K. 2684

Copy: CT 38 32; III R 2, 11

Edition: *Freedman* 2006. P. 61–67

Not in BAK

Year: 708

Text type: *Šumma ālu*, snakes tablet 22 according to the colophon, tablet 24 (*Freedman* 2006. P. 67, comm. [variant numbering of the series])

Rev.

- 1' [DIŠ MUŠ ...] ^rKÁ.⁷GAL ina x [...]
2' DUB 22.KAM ina⁰ DIŠ URU [ina SUKUD-e GAR-(in)]
3' LIBIR.RA.GI[M AB.SAR.ĀM BA.AN.]È
4' ^{tup-pi}^{md}AG—[^{zu-qu-ù}]^p—GI.NA DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-šá [^{lu}]DUB.SAR
5' ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^mr Gab-bi^r—DINGIR^{mes}-ni—KAM-eš [^{lu}]GAL DUB.SAR^{mes}
6' ^{uru}Kal-ḫa^{iti}BARÁ UD [2]4.KAM li-mu^{md}UTU—ú-pab-ḫir^{lu}GAR.KUR [Hab-ru-ri]
7' MU 14.KAM ^mLUGAL—GI.[NA] EGIR-ú LUGAL KUR [Aššur^{ki}]
8' [ù] ^rMU 2.KAM⁷ L[LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

Rev.

- 1' [If a snake...] city gate in [...]
2' 22nd tablet of *If a City [is Set on a Heigh]*.
3' Accord[ing] to its ancient original, [written (and) coll]ated.
4' A tablet of Nabû-[zuqu]p-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, [the] scribe,
5' descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, [the] chief of the scribes.
6' Kalḫu, Nisannu, [2]4th day, eponymy of Šamaš-upaḫḫir, governor [of Ḫabrūru],
7' 14th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria,
8' [and] 2nd year, [king of Babylon].

36. Museum number: K. 3070+7157+11830+12890(+)K. 3956

Copy: CT 38 37 (no colophon)

Edition: *Freedman* 2006. P. 132–143

Not in BAK

Year: 708

Text type: *Šumma ālu* tablet 30 or 31 according to *Freedman* (2006. P. 132b)

Notes: should be restored as triple dated. K. 3659 collated from the photograph graciously made for me by Jeanette Fincke. The traces of the tablet number in line 4' are indiscernible. The gloss “8” is on the edge near line 2', and apparently does not relate to the tablet number (*contra* Freedman).

K. 3956 Rev. iv

ruling

3' DIŠ EME.ŠID ŠÁ 2 KUN^[meš] GAR ina É NA IGI-ir]

4' ʾDUB X.KAM ʾ [DIŠ URU ina SUKUD-e GAR-(in)]

K. 3070 Rev. iv

1' traces of signes

2' [^{uru}KalabⁱⁱX UD Y.KÁM]i-mu^{md}UTU—ú-pab-ḫir^{lu}GAR.[KUR^{kur}Hab-ru-ri]

3' [MU 14.KÁM^m]ʾLUGAL—GI.ʾ[NA EGIR-úʾ LUGAL ʾ [KUR Aššur^{ki}]

4' [(ú) MU 2.KÁM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

Rev. iv

3' If a lizard that has two tail[s] is seen in a man's house].

4' Xth tablet (of) *If a City [is Set on a Height]*.

2' [Kalḫu, month X, Yth day, epo]nymy of Šamaš-upaḫḫir, gover[nor of H]abrūru],

3' [14th year], Sargon [the Sec]ond, king of [Assyria],

4' [and 2nd year, king of Babylon].

37. Museum number: K. 2689

Copy: III R 2, 10

Not in BAK

Year: 708

Text type: probably *Šumma ālu* (*Šumma ālu* year)

Rev.

0' [...tup-ḫi^{md}AG—zu-qu-up—GI.NA]

1' [DUMU^{md}AMAR.]ʾUTU—MU ʾ[-BA-ŠÁ^{lu}DUB.SAR ŠÀ.BAL.BAL^mGab-bi—DINGIR]ʾmeš ʾ[-ni—KAM-eš^{lu}GAL
tupšarrz]

2' [^{uru}Kal-]ḫaⁱⁱⁱBARÁ ʾ [UD 2]1[?].KÁM li-mu^{md}UTU—ú-pab-ḫir^{lu}GAR.KUR^{kur}[H]ab-ru-ri]

3' [MU 14.KÁM^mLUGAL]—GI.NA EGIR-úʾ LUGAL KUR Ašš[ur^{ki}]

4' [(ú) MU 2.KÁM] LUGAL ʾKÁ.ʾ[DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

Rev.

0' [... A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu],

1' [son of Mar]duk-šumu-[iqiša, the scribe, descendant of Gabbi-i]lā[ni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes].

- 2' [Kal]ḫu, Nisannu, [2]1st day, eponymy of Šamaš-upaḫḫir, governor [of Ḫabrūru],
 3' [14th year, Sar]gon the Second, king of As[syria],
 4' [(and) 2nd year], king of Ba[bylon].

38. Museum number: K. 2685+K. 3762+Sm. 1705

Copy: CT 40 11:102–107

Edition: *Freedman* 1998. P. 159–180

BAK 294E

Year: 708(?). Date and date formula restored based on K. 2682+K. 2684 also written in Nisannu

Text type: *Šumma ālu* 10 (*Freedman* 1998. P. 159)

Notes: should be restored as triple dated.

Rev. iv

- 102 [...]A É *šum-ma* EN É *ina-an-ziḡ*
 103 [...DUB X.KÁM DIŠ URU] *ina* SUKUD-*e* GAR 3 UŠ 45.TA.ÀM MU ŠID.IM
 104 [LIBIR.RA.BI.GIM] AB.SAR.ÀM BA¹.AN.È
 105 [*tup-pi*]^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA
 106 [DUMU^{md}AM]AR.UTU—MU—BA-*ša*^{li}DUB.SAR
 107 [ŠÀ.BAL.BAL^m*Gab-bi*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-*es*^{li}GAL DUB.SAR^{mes}
 108 [^{uru}*Kalab*^{iti}BA]RA₂.ZÀ.GAR UD 15.KÁM
 109 [*li-mu*^{md}UTU—*u-pab-bi*]^{ir}1^{li}GAR.KUR *Ḫab-ru-ri*
 110 MU 14.KÁM^mLUGAL—GI.NA EGIR-*u* LUGAL KUR *Aššur*^{ki}
 111 [(*u*)] MU 2.KÁM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}

Rev. iv

- 102 [...] ...a house. If the owner of the house will be (constantly) worried¹⁶³.
 103 [...] Xth tablet (of) *If a City* is Set on a Height, 225 lines.
 104 [According to its ancient original], written (and) collated.
 105 [A tabl]et of Nabû-zuqap-kēnu,
 106 [son of Mar]duk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
 107 [descendant of Gabb]-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes.
 108 [Kal]ḫu, Ni[sannu], 15th day,
 109 [eponymy of Šamaš-upaḫḫ]ir, g[overnor of Ḫabrūru],
 110 [14th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria],
 111 [(and) 2nd year, king of Babylon].

707

39. Museum number: K. 3066=III R 2, 12

BAK 294F

Year: 707

Text type: probably *Šumma ālu* (*Šumma ālu* year and colophon type)

Notes: should be restored as triple dated; a flake of a colophon.

- 1' [LIBIR.R]A.BI.GIM AB.SAR.ÀM BA.AN.È
 2' [*tup-pi*]^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA¹(AN) DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*ša*^{li}DUB.SAR
 3' [ŠÀ.BAL.BAL^m*Gab-bi*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-*es*^{li}GAL D]UB.SAR^{mes} ^{uru}*Kal-ba*^{iti}APIN UD 14.KÁM

4' [li-mu mŠa-dAš+šur-du-ub-bu lúGAR.]KUR uruTu-us-ḥa-an x'
 5' [MU 15.KÁM mLUGAL—GI.NA EGIR-ú LUGAL KUR] dAš+šur^{ki}
 6' [(ú) MU 3.KÁM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

1' Written (and) collated in accordance with its anc[ient original].
 2' [A tablet of Nabû-zuqup]-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
 3' [descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes. Kalḫu, Araḥsamnu, 14th day,
 4' [eponymy of Ša-Aššūr-dubbu, the gove]rnor of Tušḫan,
 5' [15th year, Sargon the Second, king]of Assyria,
 6' [(and) 3rd year, king of Babylon].

40. Museum number: K. 3074+K. 11004

Copy: III R 2, 13

Edition of the colophon: *Sallaberger W.* Das Erscheinen Marduks als Vorzeichen // *Zeitschrift für Assyriologie und Vorderasiatische Archäologie*. Vol. 90. Berlin, 2000. P. 230.

BAK 294G

Year: 707

Text type: *Šumma ālu* 120

1' [DU]B 1 ME 20.KÁM DIŠ URU ina SUKUD-e rGAR'-[in X.ĀM MU] rSID. IM
 2' LIBIR.RA.BI.GIM AB.SAR.[ĀM BA.]AN.[È tuḫ-] rpi' mdAG—zu-qu-up—GI.NA
 3' DUMU mdAMAR.UTU—rMU'—BA-šú lúDUB.SAR ŠĀ.BAL.BAL mGab-bi—DINGIR^{meš}-ni—KAM-eš lúGAL
 DUB.SAR^{meš}
 4' uruKal-ḥa iú' APIN UD 16.KÁM li-mu mŠa—dAš+šur—du-ub-bu lúGAR.KUR uruTu-us-ḥa'-[an]
 5' MU 15.KÁM mLUGAL—GI.NA EGIR-ú LUGAL [KUR Aššur^{ki}]
 6' ú MU [3.KÁM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

1' 120th [ta]blet (of) *If a City is Set on a Height*; [X] lines.
 2' Writt[en (and) co]ll[ated] in accordance with its ancient original. [A tab]let of
 Nabû-zuqup-kēnu,
 3' son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe, descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the
 scribes.
 4' Kalḫu, Araḥsamnu, 16th day, eponymy of Ša-Aššūr-dubbu, the governor of Tušḫ[an],
 5' 15th year, Sargon the Second, king [of Assyria],
 6' and [3rd] year, [king of Babylon].

41. Museum number: K. 3055+K. 12089(+)³⁰⁷⁵ (indirect join suggested by Lieberman [1987. P. 205])

BAK 294H and I

Edition: *Freedman* Academia.edu (without K. 3075)

Year: 707

Text type: *Šumma ālu* 45 in the colophon; *Šumma ālu* 49 (*Guinan* 2002. P. 14 and *Heeßel* 2002. P. 234)

Rev.

5' [DIŠ] SAL.ŠAH 1 Û.TU EN-šú UG, É.BI BIR-ah ta-lá[t-ti bu-lá] NU SI. rSÁ'
 6' DUB 45.KÁM DIŠ URU ina SUKUD-[e] GAR-in 1 UŠ 43.T[A.ĀM] MU SID.IM

- 7' [LIBIR.R]A.BL.GIM AB.SAR.ÀM [BA.AN].È
 8' [*tup-pi*^dAG]—*zu-qu-up*—GL.NA [DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*šá* *tupšar(r)*]
 9' [ŠA.BAL.BAL^m*Gab-bi*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM]—*es*^{li}[GAL DUB.]SAR^{mes}
 10' [^{uru}*Kalah*ⁱⁱX UD Y.KÁM *li-mu*^m]*ša*^d*Aš+šur—du-u*[*b-bu*^{li}GAR.KUR^{uru}*Tu-uš-ḥa-an*]
 11' [MU 15.KÁM^mLUGAL—GL.NA EGIR-*ú* LUGAL KUR *Aššur*^{ki} (*ú*) MU] 3.KÁM [LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

Rev.

- 5' [If a sow gives birth to one, her owner will die; his house will be dispersed; the off[spring of cattle] will not prosper.
 6' 45th tablet (of) *If a City is Set on a Height*, 103 lines.
 7' According to its [ancient origin]al, written (and) [coll]ated.
 8' [A tablet of Nabû-zu[qup]-kēna, [son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe],
 9' [descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēr]eš, the ch[ief of the scr]ibes.
 10' [Kalḥu, month X, Yth day; eponymy of] Ša-Aššūr-dub[bu, governor of Tušḥan],
 11' [15th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria, (and)] 3rd [year, king of Babylon].

42. Museum number: BM 131656

Copy: T. G. Pinches *apud Weidner* 1936–1937¹⁶⁴. Pl. 1.

Edition: *Weidner* 1936–1937. P. 359

Not in BAK

Year: 707

Text type: *Šumma ālu* 84

Notes: should be restored as triple dated.

- 6' DIŠ LÚ SILA *ina* DU-*šú* LÚ DINGIR *íl-ma* IGI [...]
 7' DUB 1.24.KÁM DIŠ URU *i'-na* SUKUD-*e* GAR-*in* 1 UŠ 59.TA.À[M MU ŠID.IM]
 8' LIBIR.RA.BL.GIM AB.SAR.ÀM [BA.AN.È]
 9' *tup-pi*^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GL.NA DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—[MU—BA-*šá* *tupšar(r)*]
 10' ŠA.BAL.BAL^m*Gab-bi*—DINGIR^{mes}—KAM-*es*^{li}[GAL *tupšar(r)*]
 11' [^{uru}*Kal-ḥa*ⁱⁱSIG₄ UD 10.KÁM *li-mu*^m]*ša*^d*Aš+šur—du-ub-bu*^{li}[GAR.KUR^{uru}*Tu-uš-ḥa-an*]
 12' MU 15.KÁM^mLUGAL—GL.NA EGIR-*ú* LUGAL KUR *Aš+šur*^{ki} MU 3.KÁM [LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

- 6' If a man that is going through the street (and another) man carries a god across [...]
 7' 84th tablet (of) *If a City is Set on a Height*, 119 [lines].
 8' According to its ancient original, written [(and) collated].
 9' A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-[šumu-iqīša, the scribe],
 10' descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, [the chief of the scribes].
 11' Kalḥu, Simānu, 10th day, eponymy of Ša-Aššūr-dub[bu, governor of Tušḥan],
 12' 15th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria, (and) 3rd year, [king of Babylon].

43. Museum number: K. 20700+20730

Not in BAK, compare to no. 40 (BAK 294G)

Year: 707

Text type: *Šumma ālu*

Notes: a flake with remains of the colophon and of a few more lines. Not collated at the Museum.

- 1' [...]i-ta²-bal x AR UD IM
 2' [DUB X.KÁM DIŠ URU ina SUKUD-e] GAR 32.TA.ÀM [MU ŠID.IM]
 3' [LIBIR.RA.BI.GIM AB.SAR.À]M [BA.]AN.<È> *tup-^rpi*^{md}AG[—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA]
 4' [DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*šá*^{li}D]UB.SAR ŠÀ.BAL.BAL^mGa[b-bi—DINGIR^{mes}-ni—KAM-eš^r ^{li}GAL
tupšarr]
 5' [^{uru}KalabⁱⁱX UD Y.KÁM] li-mu^mŠa—^dAš+šur—du-u[b-bu ^{li}GAR.KUR^{uru}Tu-uš-*ha-an*]
 6' [MU 15.KÁM^mLUGAL—GI.NA EGIR-ú L]UGAL KUR Aš+šur^{ki}MU 3.K[ÁM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]
- 1' [...] carries ...
 2' [Xth tablet (of) *If a City is Set [on a Height]*; 32 [lines].
 3' [According to its ancient original, w]ritt[en (and) c]ollated. A tablet of Nabû-[zuqup-kēnu],
 4' [son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the s]cribe, descendant of Ga[b]bi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes].
 5' [Kalḫu, month X, Yth day], eponymy of Ša-Aššūr-dub[bu, governor of Tušḫan],
 6' [15th year, Sargon the Second, k]ing of Assyria, 3r[d] year, [king of Babylon].

44. Museum number: K. 3064

Copy: III R 2, 14

Year: 707

Text type: probably *Šumma ālu* (*Šumma ālu* year and layout)

Notes: a flake with remains of the colophon and of few more lines.

- 1' [...] U ŠUR KU/ŠU BI
 2' [DUB X.KÁM DIŠ URU ina SUKUD-e GAR-(in) Y.TA.ÀM] MU ŠID.IM
 3' [LIBIR.RA.BI.GIM AB.SAR.ÀM] BA.AN.È
 4' [*tup-^rpi*^{md}AG—*zu-qup/qu-up*—GI.NA DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—]MU—<BA>-*šá*^{li}DUB.SAR
 5' [ŠÀ.BAL.BAL^mGab-bi/u—DINGIR^{mes}-ni—KAM-eš^r]^{li}GAL DUB.SAR^{mes}
 6' [^{uru}KalabⁱⁱX UD Y.KÁM] li-mu^mŠa—^dAš+šur—du-ub-bu ^{li}GAR.KUR^{uru}Tu-uš-*ha-an*
 7' [MU 15.KÁM^mLUGAL—GI.NA EGIR-ú LUGAL KUR Aššur^{ki}(*š*)] MU 3.KÁM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}
- 1' [...]
 2' [Xth tablet (of) *If a City is Set on a Height*; Y] lines.
 3' [According to its ancient original, written (and)] collated.
 4' [A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-]šumu-iqīša, the scribe,
 5' [descendant of Gabbilāni-ēreš], the chief of the scribes.
 6' [Kalḫu, month X, Yth day, eponymy of Ša-Ašš]ūr-dubbu, governor of Tušḫan,
 7' [15th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria, (and)] 3rd year, king of Babylon.

706

45. Museum number: K. 5281

Copy: AAT 12b; ACh Sin 21; *Verderame* 2002¹⁶⁵. Pl. VII, 6

Edition: *Verderame* 2002. P. 186

BAK 293E

Year: 706

Text type: *EAE* 6; *EAE* 6/7 (*Reiner* 1998. P. 217)

Notes: should be restored as triple dated.

Rev.

- 1' [...]
 2' [x] 'x x x x x' QA AN
 3' DUB 6.KÁM DIŠ UD AN ^{d+}En-líl [*ke-i pí... šařirma* BA.AN.Ē]
 4' *tu-pi* ^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—[GL.NA DUMU ^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-šá *tu-pšar(r)*]
 5' ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^mGab-bi—DINGIR^{mes-}n[*i*—KAM-*es* ^{li}GAL *tu-pšarri*]
 6' [^{uru}*Kalah* ⁱⁱ'] ^rZÍZ UD 22.KÁM ¹⁶⁶ *li-mu* ^mMu-[*tak-keil*—^d*Aš+šur* ^{li}GAR.KUR ^{uru}*Gu-za-na*]
 7' [MU 16.KÁM ^mLUGAL]—GL.NA EGIR-^r*ú* [LUGAL KUR *Aššur*^{ki}]
 8' [(š) MU 4.KÁM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

Rev.

- 3' 6th tablet (of) *Enūma Anu Enlil*. [Written and collated in accordance with...].
 4' A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-[kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe],
 5' descendant of Gabbi-ilān[*i-ēreš*, the chief of the scribes].
 6' [Kalḫu], Šabattu, 22nd day, eponymy of Mu[takkil-Aššūr, governor of Guzāna],
 7' [16th year, Sar[gon the Secon[d, king of Assyria],
 8' [(and) 4th year, king of Babylon].

46. Museum number: K. 3044

Copy: AAT 13a; ACh Sin 17

BAK 293D

Year: 706

Text type: *EAE* 8

- 3' [DIŠ 3]0 *ina* IGL.LAL-šú TÜR NIGÍN-*ma ka-l[a u₄-mi ...]*
 4' DUB 8.KAM DIŠ UD AN ^{d+}En-líl [...]
 5' *ke-i pi-i* ^{gis}le-^r ^{gis}bi-ni A[B.SAR.ĀM BA.AN.Ē]
 6' *tu-pi* ^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GL.N[A DUMU ^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-šá *tu-pšar(r)*]
 7' ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^mGab-bi—DINGIR^{mes-}ni—KAM-^r*es* [^{li}GAL *tu-pšarri* ^{uru}*Kalah*]
 8' ⁱⁱZÍZ UD 24.KÁM *li-mu* ^mMu-[*ak/ták-keil*—^d*Aš+šur* ^{li}GAR.KUR ^{uru}*Gu-za-na*]
 9' MU 16.KÁM ^mLUGAL—GL.NA EGIR-[*ú* LUGAL KUR *Aššur*^{ki}]
 10' *ú* MU ^r4'.KÁM [LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]
 3' [If the mo]on at its appearance is surrounded by a halo and [during] the enti[re day ...]
 4' 8th tablet (of) *Enūma Anu Enlil* [...]
 5' In accordance with the wooden tablet of tamarisk wr[itten (and) collated].
 6' A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kē[nu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe],
 7' descendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, [the chief of the scribes. Kalḫu],
 8' Šabattu, 24th day, eponymy of Muta[kkil-Aššūr, the governor of Guzāna],
 9' 16th year, Sargon the Secon[d, king of Assyria],
 10' and 4th year, [king of Babylon].

47. Museum number: K. 10084

Copy: AAT 31b, ACh Shamash 10

Not in BAK

Year: 706, but possibly 705

Text type: colophon – *EAE* 34; *EAE* 33 (Reiner 1998. P. 248)

Notes: should be restored as triple dated.

- 3' DIŠ *ina* ⁱⁱDU₆[...]
- 4' DUB 34.^rKAM^r[UD AN ^{d+}*En-lil*]
- 5' *ki-i pi-i* G[ABA.RI... *šaṭirma* BA.AN.Ē]
- 6' *tu-p-pi* ^{md}r^{AG}—*z[u-qup/ qu-up]*—GI.NA DUMU ^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*ša* ⁱ[*tu-p-sar(r)*]
- 7' ŠĀ.BAL.BAL ^m*Gab-bi*—[DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-*eš* ^{li}GAL *tu-p-sarri*^{uru}*Kalab*]
- 8' ⁱⁱGU₄ ^rUD^r 3.KAM ^rli^r-[*mu* ^m*Mu-tak-ki*—^d*Aš+šur* ^{li}GAR.KUR ^{uru}*Gu-za-na*]
- 9' MU ^r16^r.KAM ^rLUGAL^r—[GL.NA EGIR-*ú* LUGAL KUR *Aššur*^{ki}]
- 10' [(*ú*) MU 4.KAM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

- 3' If in month Tašrītu [...].
- 4' 34th tablet [(of) *Enūma Anu Enlil*].
- 5' In accordance with orig[inal from... written (and) collated].
- 6' A tablet of Nabû-z[uqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe],
- 7' descendant of Gabbi-[ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes. Kalḫu],
- 8' Ajaru, 3rd day, epo[nymy of Mutakkil-Aššūr, the governor of Guzāna],
- 9' 16th year, Sar[gon the Second, king of Assyria],
- 10' [and 4th year, king of Babylon].

705

48. Museum number: K. 3475+D'T 13+81-2-4, 327

Copy: *George* 2003¹⁶⁷. Pl. 146

Edition: *George* 2003. P. 737–738 ms N

BAK 294A

Year: 705

Text type: Gilgamesh Epic, Tablet XII

Notes: not collated; according to Andrew R. George's handcopy. Should be restored as triple dated.

- 1' DUB 12.KAM ĒŠ.GĀR ^dGIŠ-*gim-maš* ZAG.TIL.LA.B[I.ŠE AL.TIL]
- 2' LIBIR.R[A.B]I.GIM AB.SAR.ĀM BA.[AN.Ē]
- 3' *tu-p-pi* ^m[^dAG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA DUMU ^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-*ša* ⁱ[*tu-p-sar(r)*]
- 4' [ŠĀ].BAL.BAL ^m*Gab-bu*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-*eš* ^{li}GAL D[UB.SAR^{mes}]
- 5' [^u]^{ru}*Kal-ḫa* ⁱⁱŠU.NUMUN.NA UD 27.[KAM]
- 6' [*li-mu* ^mNIGIN—^dEN ^{li}GAR.KUR ^{uru}*Si-n[a-bu...*]
- 7' [MU 17.KAM ^mLUGAL—*kēnu* EGIR-*ú*] *šar* KUR ^d[*Aššur*^{ki}]
- 8' [(*ú*) MU 5.KAM] LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

- 1' 12th tablet (of the) series of Gilgameš, [completed to i]ts end.
- 2' Written (and) co[llated] according to [i]ts ancie[nt o]riginal.
- 3' A tabl[et of]Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, th[e scribe],
- 4' [de]scendant of Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of th[e scribes].
- 5' Kalḫu, Du'ūzu, 27th day,
- 6' [eponymy of Našḫir]-Bēl, governor of Sin[ābu],
- 7' [17th year, Sargon the Second], king of As[syria],
- 8' [(and) 5th year], king of Babylon.

49. Museum number: K. 6457+K. 12416+K. 14934+K. 15241+Rm. 497+80-7-19, 90

Copy: *Frahm* 1999. P. 88

Edition: *Frahm* 1999. P. 88

BAK 294S

Year: 705

Text type: Jupiter A (*Frahm* 1999. P. 88–90); *EAE* 64 (?; *Guinan* 2002. P. 13)

Rev.

1' [...] x x

2' [... LIBIR.RA.BI.(GIM) AB.SAR.ÀM] ʾBAʾ.AN.È

3' [*tup-pi*^{md}AG—*zu-qu-up*—GI.NA DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-šú^{li}]ʾDUBʾ. SAR

4' [ŠĀ.BAL.BAL^m*Gab-bu*—DINGIR^{meš}.ni—KAM-eš^{li}GAL *tupšarri*^u]ʾru*Kal-ḫa*

5' [i^{li}X UD Y.KAM *li-mu*^mNIGIN—d⁺EN^{li}GA]R.KUR^{uru}*Si-na-bu*

6' [MU 17.KAM^mLUGAL—GI.NA EGIR-ú LUGAL KUR *Aššur*^{ki} (ú) MU 5.]ʾKAM* LUGALʾ KÁ.DINGIR.RA^[ki]

Rev.

1' [...]

2' [Written (and)] collated [according to its ancient original].

3' [A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the s]cribe,

4' [descendant of Gabbī-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes]. Kallḫu,

5' [month X, Yth day, eponymy of Našḫir-Bēl, gov]ernor of Sinābu,

6' [17th year, Sargon the Second, king of Assyria, and 5th year], king of Babylon.

No date preserved

50. Museum number: K. 5278

Not in BAK

Notes: a flake; no scribe's name or date preserved, but clearly triple dated.

1' [...] x x [...]

2' [MU X.KAM*^mLUGAL—GI.NA EGIR]-ʾúʾ LUGAL KUR^d*Aššur*^{ki} ʾúʾ [MU Y.KAM LUGAL KÁ.DINGIR.RA^{ki}]

1' [...]

2' [Xth year, Sargon the Sec]ond, king of Assyria, and [Yth year, king of Babylon].

Date by the Royal Year Only

All the dates are given in accordance with Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's system: 721, year of ascension of Sargon; 709, first year of Sargon, the king of Babylon; 704, year of ascension of Sennacherib.

A. Nabû-zuqup-kēnu

713

51. Museum number: K. 2679

Copy: AAT 76b; ACh Sin 18

Edition: *Verderame* 2002. P. 184–185

Year: 713

BAK 293N

Text type: *EAE* 6

Notes: in Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's colophons *limmu* date always precedes the regnal year, but not here, thus most probably the *limmu* date is missing (line 10' is the last of the tablet, three sings are missing at its beginning and ca. 12–13 at the end; the restoration of the *limmu* date as shown below demands 19–20 sings). The other feature that distincts this colophon from the rest of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's colophons is the use of *ina* before the regnal year.

- 7' [DIŠ 30 *ina*ⁱⁱⁱBARA₂ UD 1.KÁM *ina* IGI.LAL-ŠÚ SI ZAG-ŠÚ AN-*e* *te-rat* [...]
 8' [DUB X.KÁM] UD AN^{d+} *En-líl ke-i* [pí]-*i*ⁱⁱⁱŠLE.U₅.UM GABA.RI KÁ.DINGIR.^rRA^{ki} [šafirma BA.AN.É]
 9' [*tup-pi*^{md}AG—*zu-q*]-*u-ut*—GI.NA DUMU^{md}AMAR.UTU—MU—BA-ŠÚ^{li}A.BA ŠÁ.BAL.B[AL
^m*Gab-bu/i*—DINGIR^{mes}-*ni*—KAM-*es*^{li}GAL [*tupšarr*]
 10' [x x x^u]Ka-lāhⁱⁱⁱDIRI.ŠE UD 15.KÁM MU 9.KÁM *ina* LUGAL—GI.NA EGIR[-ú] LUGAL KUR Aššur^{ki}
li-mu^{m(d)}Aš+šur-ba-ni^{li}GAR.KUR^{uru}Kalḫu]

- 7' [If the moon] at its appearance [on] the 1st day of Nisannu, [...]
 8' [Xth tablet (of)] *Enuma Anu Enlil* [written and collated] in accor[dance] with the wooden board, original from Babylon.
 9' [A tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, son of Marduk-šumu-iqīša, the scribe, descend[ant] of Gabbī-ilāni-ēreš, the chief of the scribes].
 10' [...]Kalḫu, Addaru, 15th day. 9th year, Sargon the Secon[d, king of Assyria, (and) eponymy of Aššūr-bāni, governor of Kalḫu].

B. Others**709**

52. Museum number: Rm. 2, 345

Edition: *Thompson* 1900¹⁶⁸. P. 44, no. 136S; SAA 8 501

Year: 709(?)

Text type: astrological report

Notes: Babylonian script. Apparently a landscape tablet.

Rev.

1' ⁱⁱⁱGAN[?] UD 14.KÁM MU 1.KÁM [...]2' LUGAL—GI.NA LUGAL TIN.TIR^{ki} [...]

Rev.

1' Kislīmu, 14th day, 1st year [...]

2' Sargon, king of Babylon [...].

703

53. Museum number: VAT 13977

Copy: *Fincke* 2010¹⁶⁹. P. 46Edition: *Fincke* 2010. P. 47

Year: 703(?)

Text type: astrological report

- 14 MU 2.KAM ^d30—šEŠ^{mes}—eri-b[*a šar māt Aššur*]
 14 2nd year, Sennacher[ib, king of Assyria].

701

54. Museum number: DT 104
 Copy: ACh Suppl. 18; *Verderame* 2002. Pl. 6 (no. 7)
 Edition: *Verderame* 2002. P. 127, 128
 Year: 701(?)
 Text type: *EAE* 5
 Notes: Babylonian ductus. Apparently a landscape tablet.

Rev.

- 1' [...] ṣ x x' [...]
 2' [...M]U 4.KAM* ^{md}30—[*abḫē—eriba...*]
 3' [...]x-*ki-mu*—^dPA DUB.SAR SAG.ṣKÚR² x x' [...]
 4' [...]nu *šá e-muq-qa-šú ma-'du* [...]

Rev.

- 2' 4th [ye]ar, Senn[acherib...]
 3' [...]kimu-Nabû, scribe of the land(?) ... [...]
 4' [...]nu whose army is numerous [...]

657

55. UET 6 413
 Edition: *Rochberg-Halton* 1988. P. 222, 223
 Year: 657

Notes: tablet from Babylonia in Babylonian ductus, a report produced in Babylonia for Babylonian king, but of Assyrian origin, i. e. for Šamaš-šumu-ukīn.

- 18 MU 10.KAM ^dGIŠ.NU₁₁—MU—GI.NA LUGAL ṣTIN.TIR^{ki}
 18 10th year, Šamaš—šumu—ukīn, king of Babylon.

¹ See *May N. N. Administrative and Other Reforms of Sargon II and Tiglath-pileser III // Change in Neo-Assyrian Imperial Administration: Evolution and Revolution / ed. by N. N. May, S. Svärd. Padova, 2015. (State Archives of Assyria Bulletin ; vol. 21). P. 91–106 [further *May* 2015]. Note that all dates in this article are before the common era.*

² *Ibid.* P. 95 with n. 79.

³ For the numbers of Sargon's prisms and cylinders and their distribution, see *Hurovitz V. A. Fort Sargon (Dūr Šarru-ukīn): A Portrait of the Royal Builder // Royal Assyrian Inscriptions: History, Historiography*

and Ideology : A Conference in Honour of Hayim Tadmor on the Occasion of His Eightieth Birthday. Jerusalem, 20 November 2003 / ed. by I. Eph'al, N. Na'aman. Jerusalem, 2009. P. 25–52 [further *Hurovitz* 2009], esp. 27, 28 with n. 10 (in Hebrew).

⁴ See, e.g., ND 1120 (*van Driel G. The Cult of Assur. Assen, 1969 [further *van Driel* 1969]. P. 59, 60) and Assyrian *Enūma eliš* (*Lambert W. G. Babylonian Creation Myths. Winona Lake, 2013. (Mesopotamian Civilizations ; vol. 16) [further *Lambert* 2013]. P. 5). Apart from royal inscriptions of various kinds, including prayers, hymns, and letters to gods, literary compositions**

deriving from the early Neo-Assyrian period are not known, although W. G. Lambert quotes F. Köcher, who dated seven fragments of *Enūma eliš* from Assur to the period of Assurnasirpal II (Ibid. P. 4).

There are only six Neo-Assyrian scholarly tablets dated by their colophons (*sic*; *contra* May 2015. P. 92, n. 71) to the time before Sargon: ND 4367, ND 5545, VAT 8780, IM 60017, LKA 36, and K 6068++. Three of them are those of the highest royal officials and probably members of the same scribal line. These are Issarān-mudammiq, *šangamabhyu*, the chief priest or exorcist, of Assurnasirpal II, and Marduk-..., the *ummānu* of Adad-nērārī III (CTN 4 8 = ND 4367). It is worth noting, that the former learned representative of the highest Assyrian priesthood stresses his descent from Babylonian temple officials (*šatammu*) in his colophons. The latter claims to be a scion of four generations of royal exorcists. Remarkably, together with the *ummānu* (“scholar”) and *tupšar šarri* (“royal scribe”) and even in the first place, he calls himself *rubû* (^ÜGAL, “the great one”) thus stressing his belonging to the stratum of royal magnates. D. J. Wiseman and J. A. Black pointed out that Adad-nērārī’s *ummānu* might be a descendant of Issarān-mudammiq, the aforementioned *šangamabhyu* of Assurnasirpal. The name or alias of the father of the *ummānu* of Adad-nērārī III was Bābilāiu. Then there are six generations of the same family of royal scholars with Babylonian connections (Wiseman D. J., Black J. A. *Literary Texts from the Temple of Nabû*. London, 1996. (Cuneiform Texts from Nimrud ; vol. 4). P. 5). Among the aforementioned six tablets, two were copied by Issarān-mudammiq. These are the so-called “Hemerology of Nazimarutaš” found at Kalḫu (ND 5545 = CTN 4 192; *Hulin P. A Hemerological Text from Nimrud // Iraq*. Vol. 21. London, 1959. P. 42–53; *Livingstone A. Hemerologies of Assyrian and Babylonian Scholars*. Bethesda, 2013. (Cornell University Studies in Assyriology and Sumerology ; vol. 25). P. 177, 178, 180–189) and its duplicate from the N4 library at Assur (KAR 147 = VAT 8780 = N4 (455); *Ibid.*); for the colophons of both copies see BAK 315. Marduk-..., the highly positioned descendant(?) of Issarān-mudammiq left us

the third scholarly tablet of the pre-Sargonid period, a copy of *Enūma Anu Enlil* dated to 787, which was written in Arbela (ND 4367).

The Khorsabad Assyrian King List (IM 60017), dated to 738 and found in Room 12 of the Nabû temple at Dūr-Šarrukīn (*Gelb I. J. Two Assyrian King Lists? // Journal of Near Eastern Studies*. Vol. 13/4. Chicago, 1954. P. 209–230), was also written by a scribe from Arbela (so the colophon. *Ibid.* P. 222, 229). This might be an indication that before Sargon at least in the 8th century the top Assyrian scholars were affiliated not with the capitals, but with Arbela, an important cult centre nonetheless irrelevant politically. LKA 36 is a very short (4 lines) thanksgiving dated to 733.

Manuscript A of the ritual of exorcism *Šep lemutti ina bīt ameli parāsu*, “To Block the Entry of the Enemy in Someone’s House” is dated to 750 (*Wiggermann F. A. M. Mesopotamian Protective Spirits: The Ritual Texts*. Groningen, 1992. (Cuneiform Monographs ; vol. 1). P. 1–23, 196–200 with figs. 1–6; colophon with the date BAK 563 = K.6068 rev. vi 1’–5’ = BBR 45, pl. 51, name of the scribe lost) .

Various colophons, written in the Neo-Assyrian ductus, refer to scholars of the kings prior to Sargon II, e.g., BAK 517 = Rm. 441:2 that mentions the *ummānu* of Tiglath-pileser(?) and BAK 528 = K. 8663 iv 5–6 written by the descendant of the physician of Adad-nērārī(?). Šumu-libši, Babylonian scribal ancestor, a royal lamentation priest (s.v. Šumu-libši 2, 3; PNA 3/I. P. 1294 by H. D. Baker), apparently was also the scribe of the kings Shalmaneser III of Assyria and Nabû-apla-iddina of Babylon and the chief lamentation priest (*kalamāhu*) of Esagila according to the colophons of his Assyrian descendants (Udug-ḫul, BAK 502 = K. 3054 = CT 16 38 iv 17–23; *Emesal Vocabulary* K.4240 = BAK 449 = *Borger* R. *Zum Emesal-Vokabular // dubsar anta-men. Studien zur Altorientalistik: Festschrift für W. H. Ph. Römer zur Vollendung seines 70. Lebensjahres mit Beiträgen von Freunden, Schülern und Kollegen / ed. by M. Dietrich, O. Loretz (Alter Orient und Altes Testament ; vol. 253), Münster 1998. P. 28, 29; kalû battle ritual BAK 500 = 81-2-4, 306:8’–12’ = *Elat M. Mesopotamische Kriegerituelle // Bibliotheca Orientalis*.*

Vol. 39. Leiden, 1982. P. 13–18; see *Gabbay U.* *Pacifying the Hearts of the Gods: Sumerian Emesal Prayers of the First Millennium*. Wiesbaden, 2014. (Heidelberger Emesal-Studien ; vol. 1). P. 254, 255). Similarly the colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu and of Inūrta-balissu mention their common ancestor Gabbi-ilāni-ēreš. Not only that we do not have tablets written by these scholars, but the very references to the Neo-Assyrian kings earlier than Sargon in the colophons are rather rare.

There are, of course tablets, that can be dated to the early Neo-Assyrian period based on ductus (e.g., KAL 2 9), but even with those included, the number of the early Neo-Assyrian scholarly tablets is incomparably smaller than the number of scholarly tablets from the time of Sargon and his descendants.

Three libraries were discovered that existed in the period before Sargon. Two of them belonged to the temples. These are the library of the Nabû temple at Kallû and of the Aššur temple at Assur (N1). However, only one tablet firmly dated to the time before Sargon derives from the the Nabû temple library at Kallû, the aforementioned CTN 4 192. Note that O. Pedersén carefully says that “Evidence may point to the existence of the library from around 800 BC to the end of the Assyrian Empire” (stress mine; *Pedersén O.* *Archives and Libraries in the Ancient Near East 1500–300*. Bethesda, 1998 [further *Pedersén* 1998]. P. 152). The only private library of the pre-Sargon period is N3. Two texts from this library – N3 (3 and 81) – date to the time of Tiglath-pileser III (733 and 744/734 respectively). For possible earlier dates of the other texts from this library or of their originals see *Idem.* *Archives and Libraries in the City of Assur: A Survey of the Material from the German Excavations*. Pt. 2. Uppsala, 1986. P. 35.

⁵ *Veldhuis N.* *History of the Cuneiform Lexical Tradition*. Münster, 2014. (Guide to the Mesopotamian Textual Record ; vol. 6) [further *Veldhuis* 2014]. P. 374, 375. See *Wiseman D. J.* *Assyrian Writing Boards // Iraq*. Vol. 17. London, 1955 [further *Wiseman* 1955]. P. 7 and pl. I for the cover inscription.

⁶ See *Fünke J. C.* *Babylonische Gelehrte am neuassyrischen Hof // Krieg und Frieden im Alten*

Vorderasien: 52e Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale: International Congress of Assyriology and Near Eastern Archaeology. Münster, 17.–21. Juli 2006 / ed. by H. Neumann [et al.]. Münster, 2014. (Alter Orient und Altes Testament ; vol. 401). P. 269–292, esp. 269, 270. For the absence of Assyrian astronomical reports and employment of Babylonian astrologers at the Assyrian court at the time before Sargon and for possible creating of a library by Sargon, see *Eadem.* *The Babylonian Texts of Nineveh: Report on the British Museum’s Ashur-banipal Library Project // Archiv für Orientforschung*. Vol. 50. Vienna, 2003–2004. P. 116–217 with n. 43; P. 132, n. 165). For *kalûtu* as the genre imported from Babylonia and strange to Assyria, see *Gabbay U.* *The Kalû Priest and the Kalûtu Literature in Assyria // Orient*. Vol. 49. Tokyo, 2014. P. 115–144.

⁷ *Frahm E.* *Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, das Gilgames-Epos und der Tod Sargons II // Journal of Cuneiform Studies*. Vol. 51. Atlanta, 1999. P. 73–90 [further *Frahm* 1999].

⁸ Literature was obviously not Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s field. This is the only literary composition in his collection, and it is not the best of Mesopotamian literature (*George A. R.* *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic: Introduction, Critical Edition and Cuneiform Text*. Oxford, 2003 [further *George* 2003]. P. 48). A. R. George, however, acquits Nabû-zuqup-kēnu of the responsibility for translation of Tablet XII and thus, for the low literary merits of this translation (*Ibid.* P. 49).

⁹ *Guinan A. K.* *A Severed Head Laughed: Stories of Divinatory Interpretation // Magic and Divination in the Ancient World / ed. by L. J. Ciruolo, J. L. Seidel*. Leiden, 2002. (Ancient Magic and Divination ; vol. 2) [further *Guinan* 2002]. P. 16.

¹⁰ The Synchronistic King List, see *Grayson A. K.* *Königslisten und Chroniken. B. Akkadisch // Reallexikon der Assyriologie und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie*. Vol. 6 : Klagegesang – Libanon. Berlin ; New York, 1980–1983 [further *Grayson* 1980–1983]. P. 119, Ass. 14616c iii 16–19.

¹¹ See Appendix 2, no. 1 (K. 2686+2687).

¹² K. 10379, not dated.

- ¹³ U. Koch (*Koch U. S.* The *Āšipu*-Healer and Diviner?; URL: <https://ku-dk.academia.edu/UllaSusanneKoch>, accessed: 16.07.2016) and N. Veldhuis (*Veldhuis* 2014. P. 375, 376) consider *tupšarru* to be a term for the scribal profession of astronomer-astrologer. For *tupšarru* as an abbreviation for *tupšarru Enima Anu Enlil*, “astrologer-astronomer,” see Radner K. The Assyrian King and his Scholars: The Syro-Anatolian and the Egyptian Schools // Of God(s), Trees, Kings, and Scholars. Neo-Assyrian and Related Studies in Honour of Simo Parpola / ed. by M. Luukko, S. Svård, R. Mattila. Helsinki, 2009. (Studia Orientalia ; vol. 106). P. 222, cf. SAA 10. P. XIII. This interpretation is not, however, commonly accepted. F. Rochberg translates *tupšarru* as the “scribe-diviner” (Rochberg F. The Heavenly Writing. Divination, Horoscopy, and Astronomy in Mesopotamian Culture. Cambridge, 2004. P. 95) which reflects exactly what Nabû-zuqup-kēnu was.
- ¹⁴ Appendix 2, nos. 1, 6 and 7 (K. 2686+2687, K. 2678, and K. 2683+K. 8083 respectively) and Sm. 1239.
- ¹⁵ K. 137:35’.
- ¹⁶ K. 3384+K. 5990:26–27. Since the piece of the tablet with the relevant information is broken off, it is unclear if in this colophon Nabû-zuqup-kēnu appears as the father or the grandfather of Issār-šumu-ēreš.
- ¹⁷ K. 2670, Appendix 2, no. 16. *Livingstone A.* Mystical and Mythological Explanatory Works of Assyrian and Babylonian Scholars. Oxford, 1986 [further *Livingstone* 1986]. P. 28, 29.
- ¹⁸ K. 10379.
- ¹⁹ The tablet is not dated, but since Nabû-zuqup-kēnu still bears the title of an apprentice in its colophon, it should be his early work. His earliest dated commentary is K. 8014, Appendix 2, no. 9 written in 711. For Nabû-zuqup-kēnu as the owner and author of the earliest known cuneiform commentaries see *Frahm E.* Babylonian and Assyrian Text Commentaries: Origins of Interpretation. Münster, 2011. (Guide to the Mesopotamian Textual Record ; vol. 5) [further *Frahm* 2011]. P. 266. E. Frahm estimates that the commentaries constitute about 21% of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s tablets.
- ²⁰ In the colophon of K. 2670, Appendix 2, no. 16, Issār-šumu-ēreš is called the “son” of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, but since there is no other evidence about Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s son of this name it is logical to assume that he is calling his grandson a “son” here.
- ²¹ I would like to express my deep gratitude to Ann Guinan, who generously shared with me the information about Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s tablets assembled by her. The site Cuneiform Commentaries Project (CCP: <http://ccp.yale.edu>) of Yale, created by Eckart Frahm and Enrique Jiménez does a great service to the public and to this contribution particularly. Finally, this paper would not be written without the possibility to collate the tablets with the help of the photographs published online by the British Museum and the Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative of the project of the University of California, Los Angeles, the University of Oxford, and the Max Planck Institute for the History of Science, Berlin (CDLI: <http://cdli.ucla.edu>).
- ²² See Appendix 1 for the distribution of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s texts according to genres.
- ²³ *Millard A. R.* The Eponyms of the Assyrian Empire 910–612. Helsinki, 1994. (State Archives of Assyria Studies ; vol. 2) [further *Millard* 1994]. P. 70, 71.
- ²⁴ These are Appendix 2, nos. 1–4 (K. 2686+2687; K. 3129; 1891, 5-9 Bu, 97; K. 3067). No. 2, K. 3129, is dated by the 6th year of Sargon; the name of the eponym is not preserved.
- ²⁵ Appendix 2, no. 20 (VAT 8807), *Lambert W. G.* Babylonian Wisdom Literature. London, 1960 [further *Lambert* 1960]. P. 213–220.
- ²⁶ Appendix 2, no. 21. This is obvious from the discussed below list of contemporaries of Zaia, incorporated into this text, who participated in the ritual itself. Naturally, some parts of the text of the ritual could indeed be more ancient. See *van Driel* 1969. P. 198, 199; *May N. N.* The Neo-Assyrian Scribe of the City of Assur (sic!) Zaia (sic!) and his Middle Assyrian Ancestry // *Nouvelles Assyriologiques Brèves et Utilitaires*. Paris, 2017. Vol. 3. No. 78 [further *May* 2017]. P. 138–142.
- ²⁷ G. van Driel relying on D. J. Wiseman’s handcopy (*Wiseman D. J.* The Nimrud Tablets, 1951 // Iraq.

Vol. 14/1. London, 1952. P. 61–71, esp. 69, pl. XX-III:10) read this name as *Zaia* (*van Driel* 1969. P. 200, ND 1120:10). J. N. Postgate (*Postgate J. N.* The Governor's Palace Archive. London, 1973. (Cuneiform Texts from Nimrud ; vol. 2). P. 229, ND 1120:10 = No. 246:10), who collated the text in 1973, did not amend this reading. ^m*Za-za'-a* first appeared in *Deller K.* Die Hausgötter der Familie Šukrija S. Huja // Studies in the Civilization and Culture of Nuzi and the Hurrians : In Honor of Ernest R. Lacheman on his Seventy-Fifth Birthday, April 29, 1981 / ed. by M. A. Morrison, D. I. Owen. Winona Lake, 1981. (Studies on the Civilization and Culture of Nuzi and the Hurrians ; vol. 1) [further *Deller* 1981]. P. 65. K. Deller, however, does not indicate that he collated the text. Thus it was rather emendation than collation. This emendation was incorporated into Helsinki Corpus of Neo-Assyrian texts and penetrated consequently PNA and SAA 20 55.

In March 2017 I received the photographs of ND 1120 = IM 56880 and was able to check the reading of the name of its scribe. I am most grateful to A. I. Jankowski for photographing this tablet for me and to the curators of the Iraq Museum (Baghdad) for their kind permission and assistance.

Beyond any doubt, the name of the scribe of ND 1120 should be read *Za-a-a*. That means that he is identical with *Zaia* who with the same title *tupšar ali* appears as a witness on three deeds from Assur written in this city in the reign of Sennacherib: the house purchase deed StAT 3 73 (VAT 19509 = N 28 [23]; 698), the house purchase deed VAT 10762 (692) with the seal of Aššūr-uballit, the overseer of Assur, and the land purchase deed VAT 10430 (date lost) of the scribe of the tax levy of Assur (s. v. *Zaia*; PNA 3/II. P. 1431 by E. Lipiński).

On StAT 3 73 with the seal of Marduk-iqbi, the overseer of Assur, *Zaia* is also the tablet keeper (*sabit tuppi*). StAT 3 73 demonstrates the same idiosyncratic love for long lists of details, this time the house attributes and belongings, as the genealogy of *Zaia* in ND 1120. Note that E. Lipiński and H. D. Baker (s. v. *Zāzā*, *Zāzāia*; PNA 3/II. P. 1439 by H. D. Baker) did not identify the author of royal ritual ND

1120 (Ibid. *Zāzā* 1), and *Zaia* (s. v. *Zaia* 2; PNA 3/II. P. 1431 by E. Lipiński), who appears as a witness on the aforementioned documents, despite the fact that this is obviously the same person. See also *May N. N.* Review of: The Prosopography of the Neo-Assyrian Empire, Vol. 3, Part 1: Š–Z by H. D. Baker. Helsinki, 2011 // Bibliotheca Orientalis. Vol. 53/5–6. Leiden, 2016. P. 742–744; *May* 2017. P. 138–142.

²⁸ ND 1120:10 has the name with the title ^{lu}A.BA URU and rev. 16'–20' (Appendix 2, no. 21) contains the title and the genealogy; *May* 2017. P. 138–142.

²⁹ In ND 1120 *Zaia* and his ancestors have the title ^{lu}A.BA URU/ ^{lu}DUB.SAR URU, “scribe of the city”, which is Assur and not Kalḫu, as PNA states in *Zāzā* 1 and in the entries about his ancestors: in Aššūr-bēl-ilāni 2 (PNA 1/I. P. 171 by K. Radner), Ešrāiu 1 (PNA 1/II. P. 407 by K. S. Schmid), Etel-pī-Marduk 1 (PNA 1/II. P. 407 by W. Pemke), Marduk-kabti-aḫḫēšu (PNA 2/II. P. 718 by H. D. Baker), Nabû-bēl-ilāni 1 (PNA 2/II. P. 810 by K. Kessler), and Šin-aplu-iddina 1 (PNA 3/I by M. Capraro). Nonetheless, Aḫu-rība 1 (PNA 1/I. P. 87 by K. Radner) and Ubru-Nabû 5 (PNA 3/II. P. 1366 by H. D. Baker) do not mention the place of origin of these two ancestors of the author of ND 1120, while J. A. Brinkman states that his father Bābu-aḫu-iddina comes from Assur (s. v. Bābu-aḫu-iddina 3; PNA 3/I. P. 1129). These can be due to Brinkman's identification of this individual with the witness in VAT 10696 rev. 2. However B. Faist, who recently published VAT 10696 as WVDOG 132 32, notes “Rs. komplett weggebrochen” (*Faist B.* Neassyrische Rechtsurkunden IV. Wiesbaden, 2010. (Wissenschaftliche Veröffentlichung der Deutschen Orient-Gesellschaft ; vol. 132). P. 40). The last of the ancestors of the author of ND 1120 appears in PNA twice: as Aššūr-da”inanni 3 (PNA 1/I. P. 177 by K. Åkerman) and as Aššūr-idnanni (PNA 1/II. P. 188 by M. Weszeli), both said to come from Kalḫu. All ancestors of the author of ND 1120 also bore the same title, “the city scribe”. Obviously those of them who leaved before Assurnasirpal II, which would be at least a half of them, were not the scribes of Kalḫu – then a small town that could not be home

to a famous scribal dynasty. They were the scribes of Assur, the capital of their times. Despite that the tablet was found at Kalḫu, the text clearly and repeatedly states that the ritual itself was performed at the temple of Aššur at Assur (ND 1120:3, 6, 8, 12, 14, 18, 21, 24). Nabû-šallimšunu, the scribe of the king, is said to come especially to Assur, apparently from Kalḫu, in order to participate in it. Moreover, the ritual explicitly mentions that Nabû-šallimšunu, who belonged to the royal court at Kalḫu, arrives to Assur, but it never says anything about the arrival of Zaia, the city scribe, to Assur and it is clear that he has been there already, since he lived in Assur. Finally, the family ancestor, Etel-pī-Marduk, ¹⁶DUB.SAR É *tup-pa-a-ti*, “the scribe of the tablet house”, was certainly not from Kalḫu, which hardly could have such an institution in the second millennium. In the Middle Assyrian period the Assyrian scholarship was flourishing at Assur, not at Kalḫu and the author of ND 1120 is certainly proud to be the descendant of one of his city’s most prominent scribal families; see *May* 2017. P. 138–142.

³⁰ ND 1120 rev. 21’–23’.

³¹ Appendix 2, no. 21 (ND 1120:1–2) date broken.

In Assyria the first occurrence of the expression “in the time of the king” in the date formulas of the documents together with *limmu* date belongs to the reign of Tiglath-pileser III (SAA 6 1 rev. 19–22e). However, the other two instances of such dating are attested on the deeds of the same cohort commander and later the charioteer Mannu-kī-Arbail (SAA 6 201 rev. 13–14, 680, and SAA 6 210 rev. 16–18, 676), on whose deed the last double date occurs (see below and Appendix 2, no. 30, SAA 6 212). A short (4 lines) thanksgiving is dated by the eponym date, 733, and the “time” of Tiglath-pileser III (LKA 36:5–rev. 3). A group of tablets from Huzūrīna also is dated by the eponym dates and by the “time” of Sennacherib and Esarhaddon: STT 192 rev. 26’, bilingual incantation for dedication of an ox-hide, 701; STT 33 rev. 127’–128’, lines 7–8 of the colophon, *Ludlul bel nemeqi* (Lambert 1960. P. 62), 701; STT 84 rev. 115’–116’, lines 6–7 of the colophon, *Šurpu* 4, 670; and probably a hymn, STT 71:74. The

date formula of the latter preserved only MAN KUR [Aššur^k], which in theory can be also a part of the double date, but it is hardly so given the fact that the double dates belong exclusively to the scholars from the capitals, while Huzūrīna tablets have only *ina tarḫi*. It is worth noting that on the documents the royal “time” always follows the eponym date.

³² Mayer W. Sargons Feldzug gegen Urartu – 714 v. Chr. Text und Übersetzung // Mitteilungen der Deutschen Orient-Gesellschaft zu Berlin. Vol. 115. Berlin, 1983. P. 65–132.

³³ Ibid. P. 68–69, line 6. It is also worth noting that Sargon II’s Letter to Aššur, composed by Nabû-šallimšunu, was unearthed at Assur in the library of the “exorcists”, N4 (477) in O. Pedersén’s nomenclature. This library belonged to the family of the closest colleagues of Zaia, the hereditary exorcists of the Aššur temple.

³⁴ Appendix 2, no. 22, SAA 12 19 rev. 26.

³⁵ Appendix 2, no. 24, SAA 6 31. The title of Nabû-kabti-aḫḫēšu appears in line 4, the date formula in lines 27–29.

³⁶ Postgate J. N. Fifty Neo-Assyrian Legal Documents. Warminster, 1976 [further Postgate 1976]. P. 81.

³⁷ Apparently of Kalḫu.

³⁸ K. 3068, *manzāzu*-commentary 1 (704; Appendix 2, no. 10); K. 3163, *rikis gerri* of EAE (701; Appendix 2, no. 12); K. 398, commentary on EAE 56 (a landscape tablet; 698; Appendix 2, no. 13); K. 75+K. 237, commentary on EAE 5 (?; a landscape tablet, written in Babylonian ductus; 694; Appendix 2, no. 14); and K. 14169, EAE 57 (?; 686; Appendix 2, no. 15). Sm. 1003 is a flake of a colophon (701; Appendix 2, no. 11).

³⁹ K. 2670, Appendix 2, no. 16, of which only the colophon survived. It was also a landscape tablet according to its colophon.

⁴⁰ Appendix 2, no. 25 (K. 2856+), 700.

⁴¹ Appendix 2, no. 26, RINAP 3/2 230, 690.

⁴² See Weissert E. Creating a Political Climate: Literary Allusions to *Enūma Eliš* in Sennacherib’s Account of the Battle of Halule // Assyrien im Wandel der Zeiten : XXXIXe Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale. Heidelberg, 6.–10. Juli 1992 / ed. by

- H. Waetzoldt, H. Hauptmann. Heidelberg, 1997. P. 191–202 for detailed discussion.
- ⁴³ Appendix 2, nos. 27–29: SAA 6 174, 685; SAA 6 177, 684; and SAA 6 90, 683 respectively.
- ⁴⁴ Appendix 2, nos. 27, 29: SAA 6 90 and 174.
- ⁴⁵ SAA 6 164, there called Mardû.
- ⁴⁶ Typically, two other deeds of Mannu-kî-Arbail, SAA 6 201 and 210, are also dated to the “time of Esarhaddon”. See above, note 31.
- ⁴⁷ SAA 10 128.
- ⁴⁸ On ten texts the double dates are sure (Appendix 2, nos. 1, 5, 6, 8, 10, 11, 13, 14, 16 and 18), three more have quite reliable traces of them (nos. 2, 9, 15). Appendix 2, nos. 31, 32, 36, 39, 45, 47 and 49 have traces of double dating, but can and should be restored as triple dated. Nos. 33, 34, 35, 37, 40–44, 46 and 48 have triple dating or traces of it. In fact all dated colophons of Nabû-zuqup-kênu had double or triple dates that are now broken.
- ⁴⁹ Appendix 2, nos. 20–22, 24–30. In no. 23 all the personal data of the author are broken, thus we do not know if it belonged to Nabû-zuqup-kênu or to somebody else.
- ⁵⁰ Rm. 2, 345; VAT 13977 and UET 6 413. See Appendix 2, nos. 52, 53, and 55. Strictly speaking, the last one is a report produced in Babylonia for the Babylonian king, but of Assyrian origin, i.e. Šamaš-šumu-ukîn. For two astrological reports dated by eponyms see *Finke J. C.* Astrologische Omenreporte aus Assur: Mondfinsternisse im Monat Nisannu // Assur-Forschungen: Arbeiten aus der Forschungsstelle “Edition literarischer Keilschrifttexte aus Assur der Heidelberger Akademie der Wissenschaften” / ed. by S. M. Maul, N. P. Heeßel. Wiesbaden, 2010 [further *Finke* 2010]. P. 57.
- ⁵¹ DT 104, Appendix 2, no. 54.
- ⁵² S. Zawadzki calls the eponymate “the only ‘democratic’ institution in Assyria” (*Zawadzki S.* The Question of the King’s Eponymate in the Latter Half of the 8th Century and in the 7th Century // Assyria 1995: Proceedings of the 10th Anniversary Symposium of the Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project. Helsinki, 7–11 September 1995 / ed. by S. Parpola, R. M. Whiting. Helsinki, 1997 [further *Zawadzki* 1997]. P. 383). Though it was rather “oligarchic” than democratic institution, Zawadzki’s observation that the eponymate expressed the magnates’ importance (Ibid.) is certainly correct. For Sargon’s reforms aimed at the diminishing of the importance of the magnates, see *May N. N.* *ṾAli-talimu*, or What Can Be Learned from the Destruction of Figurative Complexes? // Iconoclasm and Text Destruction in the Ancient Near East and Beyond / ed. by N. N. May. Chicago, 2012. (Oriental Institute Seminars ; vol. 8) [further *May* 2012]. P. 189–207; and *May* 2015.
- ⁵³ The last document dated with a double date is the deed from 676 (Appendix 2, no. 30, SAA 6 212).
- ⁵⁴ For a detailed discussion of the change in the king occupying the office of eponym and the significance of this, see *Zawadzki* 1997. P. 384, 386, and 387 with n. 22.
- ⁵⁵ *Vera Chamaşa G. W.* Sargon II’s Ascent to the Throne: The Political Situation // State Archives of Assyria Bulletin. Vol. 6. Padova, 1992. P. 21–34.
- ⁵⁶ *Zawadzki S.* The Revolt of 746 BC and the Coming of Tiglath-pileser III to the Throne // State Archives of Assyria Bulletin. Vol. 8. Padova, 1994. P. 53, 54; *Baker H. D.* Tukultî-apil-Ešarra // PNA 3/II. P. 1329.
- ⁵⁷ A village or town of Magganubba existed in the place or in the vicinity before the construction started. Sargon claims that he generously rewarded its inhabitants for their fields lying nearby (*Fuchs A.* Die Inschriften Sargons II. aus Khorsabad. Göttingen, 1994 [further *Fuchs* 1994]. P. 38–40, Zyl 44, 50).
- ⁵⁸ *Postgate J. N., Reade J. E.* Kalḫu // Reallexikon der Assyriologie und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie. Vol. 5 : Ia ... – Kizzuwatna. Berlin ; New York, 1976–1980. P. 304, 320.
- ⁵⁹ *Goodnick Westenholz J.* The Old Akkadian Presence in Nineveh: Fact or Fiction? // Iraq. Vol. 66 : Nineveh. Papers of the 49th Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale. Pt. 1 / ed. by D. P. M. Collon, A. R. George. London, 2004. P. 7–18.
- ⁶⁰ *Reade J. E.* The Evolution of Assyrian Imperial Architecture: Political Implications and Uncertainties // Mesopotamia. Vol. 46. Turin, 2011. P. 111.
- ⁶¹ *Parpola S.* The Construction of Dur-Sharrukin in the Assyrian Royal Correspondence // Khorsabad,

- le palais de Sargon II, roi d'Assyrie : Actes du colloque organisé au Musée du Louvre par le Service culturel. Paris, 21–22 janvier 1994 / ed. by A. Caubet. Paris, 1995. P. 49, 50.
- ⁶² *Place V. Ninive et l'Assyrie. Vol. 3 : Planches.* Paris, 1867 [further *Place* 1867]. Pl. 3.
- ⁶³ Nine of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's double and triple dated colophons refer to Sargon as “*arkû*”. These are K. 3129 (716; Appendix 2, no. 2); K. 2679 (713; Appendix 2, no. 51); K. 2680 (712; Appendix 2, no. 5); K. 2678 (711; Appendix 2, no. 6); K. 2682+K. 2684 (708; Appendix 2, no. 35); K. 2689 (708; Appendix 2, no. 37); K. 3074+K. 11004 (707; Appendix 2, no. 40); BM 131656 (707; Appendix 2, no. 42) and K. 3044 (706; Appendix 2, no. 46). Two tablets had *arkû* according to H. Rawlinson's copies: K. 2686+2687 = III R 2, 1 (716; Appendix 2, no. 1) and K. 2688 = III R 2, 9 (709; Appendix 2, no. 32), but it either is not preserved in the present state of these tablets or was restored by H. Rawlinson. A. Millard (*Millard* 1994. P. 102) read it also in K. 5281+Rm. 591+K. 1348 (706; Appendix 2, no. 45). *Arkû* does not appear either on the tablet in its present state or in L. Verderame's edition (*Verderame L. Le Tavole I–VI della serie astrologica Enūma Anu Enlil.* Messina, 2002. (Nisaba ; vol. 2) [further *Verderame* 2002]. P. 186). There are traces of *arkû* in *Šumma ālu*, scorpion divination (K. 3070+7157+11830+12890; 708; Appendix 2, no. 36). A. R. George restores *arkû* in the colophon of the XIIth tablet of the Epic of Gilgamesh (K. 3475+; 705; Appendix 2, no. 48), as do E. Frahm for the astral omens (K. 6457+; 705; *EAE* 64, Jupiter A; Appendix 2, no. 49), U. Koch for the commentary to *multābiltu* (K. 8014; 711; Appendix 2, no. 9), S. Freedman for *Šumma ālu* 45/49 (K. 3055+; 707; Appendix 2, no. 41), and J. Fincke for *EAE, rikis gerri* 6 (K. 5280+; 709; Appendix 2, no. 12). All these colophons belong to BAK 293, 294 or 297 types, and, apparently, all the colophons of these types could have *arkû* adjacent to the name of Sargon.
- ⁶⁴ VAT 8807, Appendix 2, no. 20.
- ⁶⁵ CAD A2. P. 286b, s.v. *arkû* 1.5.
- ⁶⁶ *Borger R., Fuchs A. Beiträge zum Inschriftenwerk Assurbanipals: Die Prismenklassen A, B, C = K, D, E, F, G, H, J und T sowie andere Inschriften.* Wiesbaden, 1996. P. 54, Prisms A vi 55 and F v 39.
- ⁶⁷ These are *πρόχειροι κανόνες*, generally known as the *Handy Tables*, the supplement to Ptolemy's famous *Μαθηματικὴ Σύνταξις*, or *Almagest*. For the text editions of the Ptolemaic Canon, see *Wachsmuth C. Einleitung in das Studium der Alten Geschichte.* Leipzig, 1895. P. 395; *Schmidtke Fr. Der Aufbau der babylonischen Chronologie.* Münster, 1952. (Orbis Antiquus ; vol. 7). P. 98; and *Grayson* 1980–1983. P. 101.
- ⁶⁸ The most plausible candidate for such an information transferor is Hipparchus (ca. 190 – ca. 120), a Greek mathematician and astronomer whose work is now lost. He was well versed in Babylonian astronomy and Ptolemy frequently refers to him. Note J. A. Brinkman's suggestion that the Babylonian Chronicle might be “at least mediately” the source of chronology of the Ptolemaic Canon (*Brinkman J. A. A Political History of Post-Kassite Babylonia: 1158–722.* Rome, 1968. (Analecta Orientalia: Commentationes Scientifcae de Rebus Orientis Antiqui ; vol. 43). P. 60, n. 300).
- ⁶⁹ *Frahm E. Observations on the Name and Age of Sargon II and on Some Patterns of Assyrian Onomastics // Nouvelles Assyriologiques Brèves et Utilitaires.* Paris, 2005. Vol. 2. No. 44. P. 50, n. 30; *Galter H. Sargon der Zweite. Über die Wiederinszenierung von Geschichte // Altertum und Mittelmeerraum: Die antike Welt diesseits und jenseits der Levante: Festschrift für Peter W. Haider zum 60. Geburtstag / ed. by R. Rollinger, B. Truschnegg.* München, 2006. (Oriens et Occidens ; vol. 12) [further *Galter* 2006]. P. 279–302.
- ⁷⁰ For Sargon II as the founder of the new dynasty, see *May* 2015. P. 106.
- ⁷¹ *Finkel I., Reade J. E. Assyrian Hieroglyphs // Zeitschrift für Assyriologie und Vorderasiatische Archäologie.* Vol. 86. Berlin, 1996. P. 263. I. Finkel and J. Reade believe that Sargon II's moving the capital resulted from “the desire to distance himself from his immediate royal predecessors”. See also *Galter* 2006. P. 291–294.
- ⁷² *Livingstone* 1986. P. 17–63, esp. 17, 30–33 (K. 170+), 44–48 and 62; *Lieberman S. J. A Mesopotamian*

Background for the So-Called Aggadic ‘Measures’ of Biblical Hermeneutics? // Hebrew Union College Annual. Vol. 58. Cincinnati, 1987 [further *Lieberman* 1987]. P. 174–176, 207, 214. The only dated tablet of this series is the last tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu written in 684.

⁷³ See Appendix 2, no. 16. This is only dated tablet of this series and the last tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu.

⁷⁴ Appendix 2, no. 16, line 4'. Line 2 in Livingstone's edition.

⁷⁵ See *May N. N.* The Vizier and the Brother: Sargon II's Brother and Vizier Sin-aḫu-ušur and the Neo-Assyrian Collateral Branches // *Bibliotheca Orientalis*. Vol. 74/5–6. Leiden, 2018. P. 517, 518 [further *May* 2018].

⁷⁶ *Fuchs* 1994. P. 42, Zyl 65; P. 70, Stier 79–80.

⁷⁷ K. 4024+K. 10893:28' and K. 14854:3', respectively.

⁷⁸ See *Finkel I. L.* Adad-apla-iddina, Esagil-kīn-apli, and the Series SA.GIG // *A Scientific Humanist: Studies in Memory of Abraham Sachs* / ed. by E. V. Leichty. Philadelphia, 1988 [further *Finkel* 1988]. P. 148, BM 41237+, line B 22' for the writing i.ZU.ZU for Nabû and *Geller M. J.* Incipits and Rubrics // *Wisdom, Gods and Literature: Studies in Assyriology in Honour of W. G. Lambert* / ed. by A. R. George, I. L. Finkel. Winona Lake, 2000. P. 248; *Jean C.* La magie néo-assyrienne en contexte: recherches sur le métier d'exorciste et le concept d'āšipūtu. Helsinki, 2006. (State Archives of Assyria Studies; vol. 17). P. 68–69 for *li*₉/*le*₉ in the ancestral name (BM 55148+, line 27 and Rm. 717+, line 27 in Geller's edition, rev. 4 in Jean's edition). E. Frahm points to the attestations of the writing i.ZU.ZU for Nabû in the god list Rm. 610:24 and its duplicate K. 29:23 (CT 25 35 and 36 respectively; *Frahm* 2011. P. 158, n. 758). He presumes that Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's play with signs follows that of the “colophon” of Esagil-kīn-apli. Indeed the cryptographic writing of the name of Nabû in BM 41237+ is closer to that of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's than the writing in the god lists. But the actual date of the text ascribed by its colophon to the famous Babylonian sage might be later than that of K. 8173 of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu. For

the interpretation of i.ZU.ZU standing for Nabû, see *Pomponio*, F. Nabû: il culto et la figura di un deo del Pantheon babelonese ed assiro. Rome, 1978. (Studi Semitici; vol. 51). P. 158, 159.

⁷⁹ Two tablets dated to 708 (K. 2682+K. 2684, Appendix 2, no. 35; K. 3070+7157+11830+12890, Appendix 2, no. 36) and four to 707 (K. 3074+K. 11004, Appendix 2, no. 40; K. 3055+K. 12089(+)+3075, Appendix 2, no. 41; BM 131656, Appendix 2, no. 42; and K. 20700+20730, Appendix 2, no. 43). In three cases his *Šumma ālu* tablets were not dated (Rm. 2, 286; Rm. 155, prodigies, see *Guinan* 2002. P. 38–40; and K. 4125, unpublished, *Guinan* 2002. P. 15: “sacrificial sheep behaviour”). Concerning the rest of the tablets in Appendix 1, all the dated ones are flakes or identified tablets but with the date broken off. For the description of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's *Šumma ālu* tablets, their content and discussion of their dates, see *Guinan* 2002. P. 12–16.

⁸⁰ *Ibid.* P. 16.

⁸¹ Rm. 2, 286 and Rm. 155 edited in *Guinan* 2002. P. 38–40.

⁸² K. 3074+K. 11004, Appendix 2, no. 40.

⁸³ Nabû-zuqup-kēnu probably started to write his *Šumma ālu* tablets on Nisannu 15, 708 (K. 4097 + Rm. 93 + Rm. 544, Appendix 2, no. 38; the year broken off). All these dates including the inauguration of Dūr-Šarrukīn are related to lunar phases, the numerological exploration of which was undertaken by Nabû-zuqup-kēnu in the second division of i.NAM.GIŠ.IJUR.AN.KI.A (K. 2164+K. 2195+K. 3510, *Livingstone* 1986. P. 26–28; not dated).

⁸⁴ For the inauguration of Dūr-Šarrukīn, see *Huronitš V. A.* The Inauguration of Palaces and Temples in the Assyrian Royal Inscriptions // *Orient*. Vol. 49. Tokyo, 2012 [further *Huronitš* 2012]. P. 96–98 with references to Sargon's inscriptions.

⁸⁵ *Guinan* 2002. P. 14.

⁸⁶ A. Guinan suggests that Tablet 120 was written by Nabû-zuqup-kēnu in conjunction with Sargon's participation in the Babylonian *akītu* festival, i. e., his triumphal entry to Babylon (*Guinan* 2002. P. 16), which took place on Nisannu 1, 709. But Tablet 120 was written a year and a half later.

- ⁸⁷ See the Eponym Chronicle B4 rev. 20' and B6 rev. 3–5; *Millard* 1994. P. 48; *May* 2012. P. 205, and *May* 2018. P. 507.
- ⁸⁸ On Assyrian triumphal *akitu* and its connection with the king entering the city on the chariot with the booty, accompanied by vassals bringing their tribute, see *May N. N.* Royal Triumph as an Aspect of the Neo-Assyrian Decorative Program // Organization, Representation, and Symbols of Power in the Ancient Near East : Proceedings of the 54th Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale. Würzburg, 20–25 July 2008 / ed. by G. Wilhelm. Winona Lake, 2012. P. 461–488.
- ⁸⁹ *Hurovitz* 2012. P. 98.
- ⁹⁰ *Ina arab šemē ūme mitgari* (*Fuchs* 1994. P. 184, Ann 440).
- ⁹¹ K. 4097 + Rm. 93 + Rm. 544, Appendix 2, no. 38; the year broken off. The numerological exploration of the “favourable” dates related to lunar phases was undertaken by Nabû-zuqup-kēnu in the second division of I.NAM.GIŠ.IJUR.AN.KLA (K. 2164+K. 2195+K. 3510, *Livingstone* 1986. P. 26–28; not dated).
- ⁹² K. 2164+K. 2195+K. 3510, *Livingstone* 1986. P. 22–28; not dated.
- ⁹³ K. 98+MS 2226 recently published in: *George A. R.* Mesopotamian Incantations and Related Texts in the Schoyen Collection. Bethesda, 2016. (Cornell University Studies in Assyriology and Sumerology ; vol. 32). P. 169–172. The tablet bears the longest of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's colophons. The date is broken off. Despite A. R. George's suggestion that it was written “for the perusal of Issār-šumu-ēreš” as states the colophon of K. 2670, the last tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu (684, Appendix 2, no. 16), it is more plausible that K. 98+MS 2226 dates to 708–707, when all Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's *šumma ālu* tablets were written.
- ⁹⁴ See *Place* 1867. Pl. 3.
- ⁹⁵ See, e.g., the description of Babylon by Herodotus (Hdt 1 178) or of heavenly Jerusalem by John in Revelation (21, 16).
- ⁹⁶ *Fuchs* 1994. P. 41, 294, *Zyl* 57, 61.
- ⁹⁷ *Hurovitz* 2009. P. 31 with ns. 22 and 23, 32.
- ⁹⁸ See Appendix 2, no. 48.
- ⁹⁹ See *May* 2015. P. 98–103.
- ¹⁰⁰ *Pedersen* 1998. P. 155, 156.
- ¹⁰¹ *Mallowan M.* Excavations at Nimrud (Kalḫu) // Iraq. Vol. 16. London, 1953. P. 99, pl. I; *Wiseman* 1955. P. 3–13; *Howard M.* Technical Description of the Ivory Writing-Boards from Nimrud // Iraq. Vol. 17. London, 1955. P. 14–20.
- ¹⁰² *Wiseman* 1955. P. 7 and pl. I.
- ¹⁰³ As testify the colophons of three of his tablets, see Appendix 2, nos. 45, 46, 47.
- ¹⁰⁴ *Guinan* 2002. P. 16.
- ¹⁰⁵ See above, note 31.
- ¹⁰⁶ The exclusion is the last tablet of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, K. 2670, Appendix 2, no. 16 (684), which takes 705 as Sennacherib's ascension year. Though few hands are discernible in Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's library, and it might well be that the actual copyist of this tablet was not Nabû-zuqup-kēnu himself, who in this very colophon complains about his already weak sight, examining the tablet seems to prove that it is written by the hand of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu himself. Nonetheless, it is worth noting that in the colophon of K. 2670 Nabû-zuqup-kēnu or his father is called “an exorcist” (^uM[AS².MAS²]). The colophon of the ritual written by an apprentice (K. 2856+, Appendix 2, no. 25; 700), whose name and patronymic are broken, but who claims to be the son or descendant of “an exorcist of the king of Assyria”, elaborately written as [^uMU₇]MU₇ LUGAL AŠ, also takes 705 as the year of ascension of Sennacherib. The relationship of the authors of K. 2670 and K. 2856+ should be further investigated. The copyist of the later can be one of Nabû-zuqup-kēnu's sons or grandsons.
- ¹⁰⁷ Cf. *Fuchs* 1994. P. 196, Prunk 23 and P. 232, Prunk 144.
- ¹⁰⁸ *Millard* 1994. P. 47, B4 rev. 15'.
- ¹⁰⁹ *Ibid.* P. 48, B6 rev. 11.
- ¹¹⁰ ND 1120, Appendix 2, no. 21; 714 and SAA 6 31, Appendix 2, no. 24; 709.
- ¹¹¹ K 2856+, Appendix 2, no. 25; 700; see above, note 106.
- ¹¹² SAA 6 174, Appendix 2, no. 27; 685; and SAA 6 177, Appendix 2, no. 28; 684; and SAA 6 90, Appendix 2, no. 28; 683.

- ¹¹³ RINAP 3/2 230, Appendix 2, no. 26; 690. This date is an obvious miscalculation of the scribe, who did not know to figure out Sennacherib's first year.
- ¹¹⁴ If such an inauguration indeed took place on the New Year in Assyria in the times of Sargon and Sennacherib, before the latter rebuilt Aššur's *akitu* house. See Pongratz-Leisten B. *Ina šulmi irub*. Die kult-topographische und ideologische Programmatik der *akitu*-Prozession in Babylonien und Assyrien im I. Jahrtausend v. Chr. Mainz am Rhein, 1994. (Baghdader Forschungen ; vol. 16). P. 101, 102.
- ¹¹⁵ Those are Appendix 2, nos. 1–9 and 39–47.
- ¹¹⁶ Appendix 2, nos. 10–16. Apparently, nos. 48–49 were written after Sargon's death though Nabû-zuqup-kēnu counted it as Sargon's year. See Frahm 1999.
- ¹¹⁷ A. L. Oppenheim noted that Sargon in his eighth campaign was accompanied by an astrologer (Oppenheim A. L. *The City of Assur in 714* // *Journal of Near Eastern Studies*. Vol. 19/2. Chicago, 1960. P. 137, 138).
- ¹¹⁸ Oppenheim A. L. *A Babylonian Diviner's Manual* // *Journal of Near Eastern Studies*. Vol. 33/2. Chicago, 1974. P. 197–220.
- ¹¹⁹ See Horowitz W. *The Reverse of the Neo-Assyrian Planisphere CT 33, 11* // *Die Rolle der Astronomie in den Kulturen Mesopotamiens : Beiträge zum 3. Grazer Morgenländischen Symposium*. Graz, 23.–27. September 1991 / ed. by H. D. Galter. Graz, 1993. (Grazer Morgenländische Studien ; vol. 3). P. 149–160; *Idem*. *The Three Stars Each: the Astro-labes and Related Texts*. Vienna, 2014. (Archiv für Orientforschung, Beiheft ; vol. 33). P. 224–235 for the discussion and editions.
- ¹²⁰ Reiner E. *Celestial Omen Tablets and Fragments in the British Museum* // *tikiþ santakēki mala bašmu...*. Festschrift für Rykle Borger zu seinem 65. Geburtstag, 24. Mai 1994 / ed. by S. M. Maul. Groningen, 1998. (Cuneiform Monographs ; vol. 10). P. 215–302 [further Reiner 1998].
- ¹²¹ See above, note 7.
- ¹²² See above, note 9.
- ¹²³ Fincke J. C. *The Seventh Tablet of the Rikis Gerri Series of Enūma Anu Enlil* // *Journal of Cuneiform Studies*. Vol. 66. Atlanta ; New York ; Boston, 2014. P. 129–148 [further Fincke 2014].
- ¹²⁴ See above, note 72.
- ¹²⁵ Gebhken E. *Die Serie DIŠ Šin ina tamartišu im Überblick* // *Nouvelles Assyriologiques Brèves et Utilitaires*. Paris, 2007. Vol. 1. No. 4. P. 3–5.
- ¹²⁶ al-Rawi F. N. H., George A. R. *Enuma Anu Enlil XIV and Other Early Astronomical Tablets* // *Archiv für Orientforschung*. Vol. 38–39. Vienna, 1991–1992. P. 52–73.
- ¹²⁷ Koch-Westenholz U. S. *Babylonian Liver Omens. The Chapters Manzāzu, Padānu and Pān Takalti of the Babylonian Extispicy Series mainly from Aššurbanipal's Library*. Copenhagen, 2000 [further Koch-Westenholz 2000].
- ¹²⁸ Koch U. S. *Secrets of Extispicy. The Chapter Multābiltu of the Babylonian Extispicy Series and Niširti bārūti Texts Mainly from Aššurbanipal's Library*. Münster, 2005 [further Koch 2005].
- ¹²⁹ [BE GÚ.MUR BÀ KILTA KAR A.M]AH *ib-bat-taq-ma bi-ib-lum* KUR *ib-bal*. For the parallel see *Ibid*. P. 173. Note that U. Koch points out that *multābiltu* 12–13 is arranged similarly to tablet 10 of the *Lung* (chapter 9 of the *Multābiltu* Catalogue; *Ibid*. P. 172).
- ¹³⁰ Freedman S. M. *If a City is Set on a Height*. The Akkadian Omen Series *Šumma Ālu ina Melē Šakin*. Vol. 1 : Tablets 1–21. Philadelphia, 1998. (Occasional Publications of the Samuel Noah Kramer Fund ; vol. 17) [further Freedman 1998].
- ¹³¹ Freedman S. M. *If a City is Set on a Height*. The Akkadian Omen Series *Šumma Ālu ina Melē Šakin*. Vol. 2 : Tablets 22–40. Philadelphia, 2006. (Occasional Publications of the Samuel Noah Kramer Fund ; vol. 19) [further Freedman 2006].
- ¹³² Heesfel N. P. *Review of: If a City is Set on a Height*. The Akkadian Omen Series *Šumma Ālu ina Melē Šakin*. Vol. 1 : Tablets 1–21, by Sally M. Freedman // *Archiv für Orientforschung*. Vol. 48–49. Vienna, 2001–2002. P. 232–241 [further Heesfel 2002].
- ¹³³ Freedman S. M. *Shumma Alu, Tablet 49, pig omens* (URL: https://www.academia.edu/15481888/Shumma_Alu_Tablet_49_pig_omens; accessed: 23.07.2017) [further Freedman Academia.edu].

- ¹³⁴ Koch U. S. Notes on a *nishu* for the performance of ornithoscopy // *Nouvelles Assyriologiques Brèves et Utilitaires*. Paris, 2015. Vol. 2. No. 47. P. 3–5.
- ¹³⁵ “Footmark”, cf. CAD Š2. P. 306a, s. v. *šepu* 6. Note BE *na-kaḫ* 15 SAGŠU MUR in VAT 9934 iv 51. See Heeßel N. P. *Divinatorische Texte II. Keilschrifttexte aus Assur literarischen Inhalts*. Vol. 5. Wiesbaden, 2012. (Wissenschaftliche Veröffentlichungen der Deutschen Orient-Gesellschaft ; vol. 139). P. 40.
- ¹³⁶ For the use of AŠ instead of DIŠ as a personal determinative in Nabû-zuqup-kēnu’s colophons, see cryptographic colophons of K. 8173 and K. 4024+K. 10893 and K. 14854, *SIT mukallimtu*-commentaries 1 and 4 respectively. Besides Nabû-zuqup-kēnu, for the use of AŠ as a personal determinative, see BM 47463 (81-11-3, 168; *Finkel* 1988. P. 149 with n. 57 and p. 154 with n. 83; *Livingstone* 1986. P. 259) and K. 5981 treated by *Lambert W. G. Ancestors, Authors, and Canonicity // Journal of Cuneiform Studies*. Vol. 11. New Haven, 1957. P. 5, n. 21. Note the use of rare signs and writings in the BAK 297 type colophons, as well as Babylonian form of some signs within the text written in Assyrian ductus.
- ¹³⁷ The realization of this name remains unknown; for other problematic readings including ^dIB(=URAŠ/URTA), see *Borger R. Mesopotamisches Zeichlexikon*. Münster, 2010. (Alter Orient und Altes Testament ; vol. 305). P. 424, 425, no. 807. Apparently, the copyist failed to copy correctly the Babylonian signs of the original. On the other hand, it might be Amēl-illulija (^mLÚ-*il-lu-li-ia*) considering that the Babylonian form of the sign LÚ was repeated by the copyist as was the Babylonian forms of the sign GIR in line 3’ and of sign ŠÁ in line 7’. But to the best of my knowledge, there is no attestations of the names of this type.
- ¹³⁸ Cf. *Koch* 2005. P. 308, no. 33 rev. 17; *Koch-Westenholz* 2000. P. 195, no. 27 A 23: BE GIR ...GIM ^{BS}BAN.
- ¹³⁹ For parallels, see ACh Sin 35:29; CT 38 49:33 and CT 39 9:3–4 (Standard Babylonian *Šumma ālu*).
- ¹⁴⁰ See above, note 23.
- ¹⁴¹ For DIRI = *malū*, see *Reiner E., Pingree D. E. Babylonian Planetary Omens*. Pt. 2 : *Enuma Anu Enlil*, Tablets 50, 51. Malibu, 1981. (Bibliotheca Mesopotamica ; vol. 2, fasc. 2). P. 85, and *Reiner* 1998. P. 280.
- ¹⁴² Only the sign ú in the name of the star is certain.
- ¹⁴³ See above, note 17.
- ¹⁴⁴ See *Livingstone* 1986. P. 34.
- ¹⁴⁵ There are traces of some unidentifiable signs in this line.
- ¹⁴⁶ See above, note 25.
- ¹⁴⁷ See above, note 27.
- ¹⁴⁸ See above, note 4.
- ¹⁴⁹ See above, note 27.
- ¹⁵⁰ Restoration of the name based on line 10 of the same tablet.
- ¹⁵¹ The other possible restoration is [^mGAN.GAN.]Ē, Kislimu. See *van Driel* 1969. P. 72; *Deller* 1981. P. 66 restores [^mAB.BA].Ē. SAA 20 55 restores [ITU.AB.BA].Ē and translates [Kis]jev (IX) sic!.
- ¹⁵² Note that the same name was borne by the representative of the forth generation of the priests of Nergal in the five-tire geneology of the high priest of Aššur in the colophon of the royal *akītu*-ritual (VAT 8882[= KAR 215]+10464=SAA 20 25) found in the library of Aššur temple at Assur (N1[7]), probably from the time of Sennacherib PNA. P. 171 s. v. Aššūr-bēl-ilāni 1 and 2 by K. Radner. This ritual involves the *qersu* and *būt abūsāte* (VAT 8882+10464 rev. vi 3 and i 7’ respectively) as does also ND 1120:7, 19, 22.
- ¹⁵³ So III R 2, 8. If it indeed is ^{lu}GAR then it is written in Babylonian ductus or, more probable, imitating it.
- ¹⁵⁴ *Radner K. Erntearbeiter und Wein: Neuassyrische Urkunden und Briefe im Louvre // State Archives of Assyria Bulletin*. Vol. 11. Padova, 1997. P. 3–29.
- ¹⁵⁵ *Borger R. Die Weihe eines Enlil-Priesters // Bibliotheca Orientalis*. Vol. 30. Leiden, 1973. P. 163–176.
- ¹⁵⁶ This is apparently a cryptographic writing playing on NIR in the next line, which is a second part of GIŠIMMAR.
- ¹⁵⁷ *Grayson A. K. The Walters Art Gallery Sennacherib Inscription // Archiv für Orientforschung*. Vol. 20. Vienna, 1963. P. 83–96.
- ¹⁵⁸ Governor of Quwê.
- ¹⁵⁹ In SAA 6 90 two individuals are mentioned: Martu’, cities’ or villages’ manager of the queen, and

Mardû, both servants of the governor of Barhalza. Which of them is identical with Mardû, cities' or villages' manager of the queen, in SAA 6 164 is unclear. See also SAA 6 164, *Kessler K., Parpola S. Mardû* // PNA 2/II. P. 704; *Baker H. D., Schmitt P. Martu'* // Ibid. P. 742.

¹⁶⁰ See the previous note.

¹⁶¹ The incipit of the following, seventh *rikis gerri* tablet. Restored upon *Iqqur ipus* § 81. See *Fincke* 2014. P. 134, 135 with n. 35.

¹⁶² See above, note 126.

¹⁶³ *Freedman* 1998. P. 173: “[...] of the house; if (it refers to) the owner of the house, he will have trouble”.

¹⁶⁴ *Weidner E. F. Keilschrifttexte nach Kopien von T. G. Pinches. Aus dem Nachlass veröffentlicht und bearbeitet* // *Archiv für Orientforschung*. Vol. 11. Vienna, 1936–1937. P. 358–360.

¹⁶⁵ See above, note 63.

¹⁶⁶ According to *Verderame* 2002. P. 186, the tablet is broken though traces of six or seven indiscernable signs are visible.

¹⁶⁷ See above, note 8.

¹⁶⁸ *Thompson R. C. The Reports of the Magicians and Astrologers of Niniveh and Babylon*. London, 1900.

¹⁶⁹ See above, note 50.